

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

**D2.4 FINAL REPORT ON QUESTIONNAIRES,
DEVELOPED COURSES AND AWARENESS
EVENTS**

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Executive Summary

D2.4 Final report on questionnaires, developed courses and awareness events

This report summarises the implementation and outcomes of key activities under WP2 of the AGEMERA project, aimed at increasing awareness and societal engagement related to critical raw materials (CRMs). This deliverable covers four core components: the design and analysis of questionnaires, the development and delivery of university courses, the organisation of public awareness events, and the execution of targeted social media and video-based campaigns.

This deliverable should be read in combination with *D2.3 2nd year evaluation report on questionnaires, developed courses and events*.

Questionnaire surveys were used as diagnostic and evaluative tools to assess public awareness, social acceptance, and stakeholder perceptions of CRM-related issues. These instruments were distributed before and after educational and outreach activities to measure changes in knowledge and engagement levels. In total, more than 1000 respondents participated in final survey. The final survey results revealed regional variation in awareness, with a general lack of understanding among younger audiences and non-experts. While participation in Germany and Finland enabled a meaningful analysis of public perceptions, low engagement in Estonia – largely due to local sensitivities and limited distribution – meant the dataset could not be used for broader conclusions. The surveys underscored the need for trust-building, clear communication, and context-sensitive outreach, particularly in regions with contested mining histories.

The **AGEMERA university courses** were developed to provide flexible, high-quality training aligned with industry needs and the EU's green and digital transition goals. The TU Freiberg (TUBAF) course "European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition" and the Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) micro-degree "Sustainable Exploration, Mining and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources" offered interdisciplinary content combining geology, sustainability, policy, and circular economy. Delivered in hybrid and online formats, the courses reached a broad audience of learners, including students and professionals. The TalTech micro-degree has been delivered twice since September 2024 and will continue in autumn 2025, with 37 registered participants as of 10 July 2025. Feedback from both programmes indicated a high level of satisfaction with the quality and structure of the content, and many participants expressed interest in further training.

Public awareness events were organised in Estonia, Germany, Finland, Bulgaria, Zambia, and online, using formats such as workshops, seminars, and stakeholder dialogues. Events targeted students, educators, citizens, and industry professionals. Emphasis was placed on inclusivity, open discussion, and stakeholder participation. Feedback collected through surveys indicated increased awareness and constructive dialogue,

although engagement challenges – particularly in free educational offerings – highlighted areas for improvement in participant retention and motivation. A key success was the engagement of secondary school teachers and students, particularly through TalTech’s interactive workshop “Minerals Got Talent: Where Does the Fork Come From?” which sparked continued discussions long after the events concluded. In Germany, TUBAF observed growing interest from local communities for inclusion in decision-making processes and more transparency from mining companies. Events in Bulgaria coincided with Earth Day and the Sofia Science Festival, where AGEMERA was showcased to a wide public audience. In Zambia, the final results seminar fostered cross-continental dialogue between stakeholders from Europe and Africa on responsible mineral development. In Finland, the Researcher’s Night brought more than 400 visitors with various ages to the “Where does the Fork Come from?” workshop.

In parallel with physical events and academic outreach, AGEMERA employed a comprehensive digital communication strategy to expand awareness and engagement through social media and video campaigns. The #AGEMERAexplains campaign presented key concepts such as "strategic minerals" or "twin transition" in plain language using visual carousels, ensuring accessibility to non-specialist audiences. The project also released several professionally coordinated videos – subtitled in multiple languages – highlighting environmental and social dimensions of CRM exploration, including the use of non-invasive technologies. These videos, published on the project’s YouTube channel and disseminated via social media, accumulated over 1800 combined views. Specific technology-focused content showcased innovations such as drone-based geophysical surveys and muon imaging. Additionally, AGEMERA leveraged International Days (e.g. World Day for Safety and Health at Work) to align CRM outreach with global awareness moments, reinforcing the project’s relevance and boosting engagement across platforms.

AGEMERA’s awareness and engagement activities were further enhanced through strategic collaborations at European and international levels. As a founding member of the European Sustainable Mining & Innovation Network (ESMIN), and an active participant in major forums such as the EU Supercluster Lapland Geoconference, EGU General Assembly, and UNECE Resource Management Week, AGEMERA extended its influence well beyond the project’s immediate scope. Through joint outreach with Horizon Europe peer projects, contributions to Smart Specialisation Platform (S3P) Mining Regions, and participation in global events like PDAC 2025 and OECD initiatives, AGEMERA positioned itself as a trusted actor at the intersection of science, society, and policy. These partnerships have helped align the project with broader sustainability agendas and ensured that its results contribute meaningfully to regional development, institutional practice, and responsible resource governance.

Overall, Deliverable D2.4 reflects AGEMERA’s proactive and multi-dimensional approach to bridging the gap between technical knowledge, public awareness, and educational outreach. The findings point to several critical conclusions:

- The views of local people on mining and exploration should be systematically monitored. They are the people who experience the potentially negative impacts of the mining sector, for example on other industries or the environment.
- Governments have a responsibility to monitor and respond to the state of the environment and the impacts experienced by local people.
- There is a notable lack of open, proactive communication from the CRM sector, which contributes to public mistrust.
- Citizens want more access to clear, accessible information and forums where they can voice concerns and receive responses from relevant authorities and companies.
- Interdisciplinary education is essential – not only for geologists and engineers but also for decision-makers, environmental experts, and the public – to navigate the complex challenges of Europe’s CRM ambitions.

By integrating research, education, and outreach, AGEMERA contributes to building a more informed, responsible, and participatory framework for CRM development in support of Europe’s strategic autonomy and sustainability goals.

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List of Acronyms

AGEMERA	Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASM	Artisanal and Small-scale Mining
BAS	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
COA	Certification of Attendance
CRMA	Critical Raw Materials Act
CRM	Critical Raw Material
CRMs	Critical Raw Materials
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
D 2.3	AGEMERA deliverable 2.3 “2ND YEAR EVALUATION REPORT ON QUESTIONNAIRES, DEVELOPED COURSES AND EVENTS”.
DGGV	German Geological Society
ECRMs	European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
EGT	Geological Survey of Estonia
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEONARDO	Geonardo Environmental Technologies
HEI	Higher Education Institution
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SLE	Social Licence to Explore
SLO	Social Licence to Operate

TalTech	Tallinn University of Technology
TT	Tallinn University of Technology
TUBAF	TU Bergakademie Freiberg
UL	University of Lapland
UN	United Nations
UNFC	United Nations Framework Classification
UNRMS	United Nations Resource Management System
UNZA	University of Zambia
UO	University of Oulu

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1 Introduction

Amid the accelerating energy transition in the European Union (EU) – driven by the Green Deal 2030 and the overarching Green Transition agenda – there is an urgent need to integrate climate-friendly and resource-efficient practices across member states. Central to this effort is the newly enacted Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), which mandates a significant increase in the domestic supply of critical materials to support both the green transition and Europe’s strategic autonomy. (European Commission, 2023)

Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) are indispensable for high-tech and clean-energy applications – ranging from electric vehicles and renewable energy systems to digital infrastructure and advanced manufacturing – making them key to Europe’s industrial and environmental ambitions. Recognising this, the EU has set ambitious targets for 2030: at least 10% of annual CRM demand should come from domestic extraction, 40% from processing, and 25% from recycling – while ensuring no more than 65% of any strategic material is sourced from a single third country. (European Commission, 2023)

Beyond supply-chain and technological considerations, enhancing public awareness, societal engagement, and interdisciplinary education on CRMs is critical. Transparency and community involvement support the social license to explore\operate (SLE\SLO) which is essential in securing public trust for mining and exploration initiatives – especially given their environmental, cultural, and societal implications. (European Commission, 2024)

The EU-funded AGEMERA project (Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials) seeks to address these multifaceted challenges. By adopting a holistic approach that combines geo-modelling, educational outreach, and stakeholder engagement, AGEMERA supports Europe’s strategic goals while fostering sustainable practices and strengthening community trust across the CRM value chain.

Objectives of the Report

This report is structured around three core thematic objectives that reflect the project’s efforts to strengthen education, public engagement, and awareness related to CRMs. These objectives include the implementation of the final questionnaire surveys in the three case study regions (Estonia, Germany, and Finland), the development and evaluation of the university-level course European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs), and organising public awareness events, seminars, and workshops addressing the role of CRMs in modern society.

1. Final Questionnaire Survey

The first objective focuses on the final questionnaire survey conducted in the case study regions to assess public awareness, perceptions, and social acceptance of mining and

CRM-related topics. These surveys were designed to function as both diagnostic and evaluative tools and were administered before and after various educational and outreach activities. This allowed for a comparative analysis of changes in knowledge, engagement, and attitudes over time. The section also discusses modifications made to the questionnaire design compared to previous versions, including the removal of map-based questions to improve clarity and accessibility. Attention is also given to the selection of survey platforms, which were chosen based on regional accessibility and institutional availability, as well as the communication strategies used to reach diverse respondent groups.

2. Launch of University Courses

The second objective addresses the launch and implementation of the ECRMs university courses. These courses were developed to integrate the latest field-specific knowledge into higher education and to foster interdisciplinary learning in support of Europe's green and digital transformation goals. This section discusses how the courses were communicated and delivered, evaluates participation and feedback from students, and analyses the courses' overall effectiveness in achieving learning outcomes. It also reflects on lessons learned, identifies potential areas for improvement, and provides an outlook for the future development of CRM-related curricula in higher education.

3. Public Awareness Events

The third and final objective of the report highlights the organisation of public awareness activities, including workshops, seminars, and events designed to promote knowledge and dialogue on CRMs and their significance. This section provides an overview of the key themes addressed during the events, outlines the intended target audiences and outreach goals, and reflects on the communication approaches employed to maximise engagement. Additionally, it summarises the feedback collected through participation questionnaires, offering insight into public interest, perceptions, and knowledge uptake related to critical raw materials.

2 Final Questionnaire Survey

The final questionnaire survey was conducted across the case study regions to evaluate public awareness, perceptions, and social acceptance of mining and CRMs. Administered both before and after outreach activities, it served as a tool to measure changes in knowledge and engagement. The questionnaire was revised from its original version to improve clarity and adapted to local conditions using regionally accessible platforms and tailored communication strategies to encourage broader participation.

The initial launch, covering Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia, yielded 1,068 completed responses, 849 partial submissions, and over 1,100 early exits. To improve data quality and response rates, the questionnaire was updated and relaunched. The following sections present the structure, implementation process, and key findings from this final round.

2.1 Case Study Areas

The final questionnaire survey focused on three main case study regions: Estonia, Germany, and Finland. This selection reflects a refinement of the geographic focus compared to the initial launch, which included Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia. Finland, where a pilot version of the questionnaire had already been conducted earlier, was included in the final round to build on existing insights and ensure continuity in data collection. The chosen regions represent a diverse cross-section of European mining contexts and public engagement with CRMs, allowing for a comparative analysis of awareness, acceptance, and regional perspectives. The survey was carried out by responsible partner institutions in each country:

- Estonia, Tallinn University of Technology,
- Germany, Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg (TU BAF),
- Finland, University of Lapland and University of Oulu.

2.1.1 Estonia

The survey was carried out in northeastern Estonia, specifically in the area surrounding Rakvere (Lääne-Viru County). This region includes ten municipalities and is home to approximately 65,000 residents. Known for its rich history and cultural heritage, the area features valuable agricultural land and archaeological evidence of human settlement dating back to 8700 BC.

During the Soviet era in the 1970s and 1980s, proposed phosphorite mining projects in the region sparked significant public opposition, leading to widespread environmental

activism and political engagement (Liivik, 2022). These events played a key role in shaping long-term public awareness of ecological and mining-related issues.

In recent years, renewed interest driven by European mineral policy has prompted the Geological Survey of Estonia (EGT) to revisit local deposits of phosphorite and graptolite argillite (Geological Survey of Estonia, 2023; Sophie Graul, 2024). The region also hosts active construction material quarries and lies close to the established oil shale industry in Ida-Viru County.

2.1.2 Germany

The Ore Mountains (Erzgebirge) in Saxony, Germany, have a mining history that stretches back over 850 years. It began with the discovery of silver in 1168 near the settlement of Christiansdorf, later renamed Freiberg, which had been founded just a few years earlier by Otto II “the Rich,” Margrave of Meissen. With strong support from the Margraves of Meissen, this discovery triggered the first *Berggeschrey*, a German term for the local mining rush taking place in Saxony. This marked the beginning of a long and influential mining tradition that has shaped the region’s landscape, economy, and cultural identity to this day. (Silberstadt® Freiberg, n.d.)

Successive mining booms followed, including major silver, tin, cobalt, and uranium extraction phases. Especially during the Cold War, uranium mining under Soviet oversight reached massive scales, employing over 400,000 people and leaving behind significant environmental challenges. (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe, n.d.)

Following reunification in 1990, large-scale mining declined, and the region faced economic restructuring and environmental rehabilitation led by the legal successor, the Wismut GmbH. Yet, since 2010, a “fourth *Berggeschrey*” has emerged due to global demand for critical raw materials essential for the green and digital transition. (Wirtschaft in Sachsen, 2024)

Currently, Saxony oversees over 15 companies active in exploration and mining operations for ores and spars in the “Free State of Saxony”.

Mining continues to influence local traditions, dialects, architecture, and annual festivals such as the *Bergparade* and *Bergstadtfest*. While mining offers economic revitalisation, local debates reflect tensions between heritage preservation, environmental concerns, and raw material demand.

2.1.3 Finland

The Finnish case study is located in the municipalities of Rovaniemi, Posio and Kuusamo in Northern Finland. Additionally, supporting interviews are conducted in Käylä village, Kuusamo.

Finland's status as a target for foreign mining investments has strengthened since its EU membership, leading to heightened foreign interest in the country's mineral resources. In the late 1990s and early 2000s, national favourable policy developments also contributed to this growth. Currently, Europe's green transition is increasing demand for critical minerals, and its effects are visible in northern Finland. In 2023, Finland became a leading mining investment destination, with foreign companies, and in 2022, approximately 81% of Finland's ore exploration by multinational companies was concentrated in Lapland.

The EU's CRMA, which took effect in 2024, aims to improve Europe's self-sufficiency in raw materials and speed up the licensing processes for strategically important projects. Especially in northern Finland, this has sparked more interest among international mining companies, where much of the country's critical mineral resources are found. Despite this rising interest, no new mines were opened in Finland in 2024.

Rovaniemi and Posio municipalities are situated in the region of Lapland whereas Kuusamo municipality exists in Northern Ostrobothnia in Northern Finland. The municipalities, with their captivating northern nature and manifold work and study prospects, offer diverse opportunities for businesses and entrepreneurs.

Rovaniemi is an expanding administrative and commercial centre in Lapland. Kuusamo and Posio, which neighbour Kuusamo, are both sparsely populated municipalities characterised by population decline. Kuusamo boasts a robust and growing international tourism sector, ranking among the most visited destinations in Finland due to its unique natural features and national parks. The area is sustained by nature-based tourism, as well as by professional fishing, reindeer herding, and hunting. (Mäntymaa et al., 2021)

Municipalities' regional development is conducted through regional council of Lapland for Rovaniemi and Kuusamo through regional council of Oulu. Both in Rovaniemi and in Kuusamo municipalities, the service industry and tourism industry are the main employers in municipalities. Foreign investment is important for regional development, especially due to municipalities' natural resources and mineral resources, which have targeted international extractive industries to both municipalities.

Currently, interests of the foreign mining industries for critical raw materials are visible in both municipalities along with increased with the growth of international tourism in both municipalities. Also, the low-carbon energy transition is reflected, among other things, in the increase in new and renewable forms of energy, such as solar power and wind power, and the electrification of transport and heating.

2.2 Questionnaire Formulation and Platforms Used

The platform for the final questionnaire survey was changed due to the expiration of the previous license and the fact that certain features, such as map-based questions, were

no longer necessary. The new platforms were selected based on accessibility for participants in each country or availability through partner universities, ensuring smoother distribution and user experience.

2.2.1 Estonia

The questionnaire used in Estonia was created with Microsoft Forms, a widely adopted platform in the country and the official survey tool at TalTech (Figure 1). It is easily accessible to the public and user-friendly. The questionnaire was adapted from the initial version of the survey, with map-based questions removed and overall content revised to improve clarity and ease of response.

When you submit this form, it will not automatically collect your details like name and email address unless you provide it yourself.

Aitäh, et olete valmis osalema meie uuringust!

Tegemist on Euroopa Komisjoni poolt rahastatud rahvusvahelise AGEMERA projekti kordusküsimustikuga. Uuringu esimene etapp viidi läbi 2024. aasta veebruarist maini. Selle käigus kogutud tagasiside põhjal täiendati ja lihtsustati küsimustikku. Teise etapi küsimustiku eesmärk on hinnata muudatuste mõju vastustele ja saadud tulemusi seejärel analüüsida.

AGEMERA projekti eesmärk on leida uusi uuringumeetodeid ja tehnoloogilaid Euroopa Liidu maavarade väärindamiseks, parandada avalikkuse teadmisi kriitiliste toorainete rollist ning toetada maavarade uuringuid, mis anevastavad keskkonna ja ühiskonna heaoluga. Eestis on projekti esindajaks TalTechi geoloogia instituut, kelle roll piirdub küsitluse levitamisega ja teavitustegevustega Euroopa kriitiliste maavarade kohta. Küsitlust viiakse läbi paralleelselt lisaks Eestile ka Saksamaal ja Soomes.

Küsimustiku täitmine võtab aega umbes 10 minutit.

Uuringu andmeid kogutakse, töödeldakse ja kasutatakse kooskõlas isikuandmete kaitsse üldmääruse (GDPR) ning rangete eetiliste põhimõtetega. Küsitlus on anonüümne. Kui Te mingil põhjusel ei soovi mõnele küsimusele vastata, võite need vahele jätta ning jätkata ülejäänud küsimustega.

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Figure 1. Question platform used for the final questionnaire by TalTech.

2.2.2 Germany

For the German case study, the re-launched/final version of the questionnaire was implemented using LimeSurvey. At TUBAF, LimeSurvey is available free of charge to all university members, providing an accessible and institutionally supported tool for conducting online surveys which has facilitated conducting the survey.

The questionnaire was carefully translated into German and adapted to the local socio-economic context to ensure relevance and clarity for respondents in the region. Where

applicable, the survey incorporated the names of locally known companies, increasing contextual accuracy and improving participant engagement.

LimeSurvey's support for customizable and multilingual questionnaire design, along with its broad range of question types, enabled the development of a well-structured and user-friendly survey. All components of the questionnaire were successfully implemented without major technical issues, and the final version effectively reflected the intended design, content, and visual layout in alignment with the research objectives.

2.2.3 Finland

The questionnaire was made using Webropol, which is perhaps one of the most widely used questionnaire platforms. The data was analysed using the SPSS software. The survey followed the framework of the pilot survey. A few changes were made to the final questionnaire to gather more detailed background information from the respondents. Also, some new questionnaire items were added. These included questions on whether the respondents have been in contact to the mineral exploration companies or have they been contacted, whether activities of the mining sector in nature conservation areas are acceptable, and whether the respondents are willing to pay higher prices for products that have been manufactured with responsibly produced minerals.

2.3 Privacy Policy

The final questionnaire survey continued to follow the same privacy policy established for the initial survey and described in Deliverable 2.3. Since the existing policy already addressed all relevant legal and ethical considerations, including compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), no new version was required. The privacy policy template used for this purpose is provided below.

EU General Data Protection Regulation

Date: DD/MM/YY

Information for research participants, respondents of the questionnaire

'Full name of the partner organisation' studies local people's views on the mineral industry (mineral exploration and mining) as part of the AGEMERA project funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement 101058178). The research areas are 'case study names of the partner.'

This privacy notice emphasises that participation in the questionnaire survey is entirely voluntary. There will be no negative consequences for anyone if they choose not to participate in the research or decide to withdraw at any time. However, if

someone withdraws from the study, the data collected before the withdrawal can still be used in the research. For more information regarding your rights and how you can affect the processing of your personal data, please see the end of this notice.

Data controller

Add 'Partner organisation name', 'address' and contact persons from the responsible local/case study-related partners who can respond to questions and provide other relevant contact information within the organisation and project.

Description of the research project and purpose of personal data processing

The data will be collected through a web-based questionnaire platform. The survey is designed to gather unique and valuable perceptions of mineral exploration and mining from the local respondents. It includes questions about the acceptance of ore exploration and mining, the effects of ore exploration and the distribution of benefits and harms, the possibility of participating and influencing decision-making, and compensation for potential harms caused by materials exploration and extraction. The personal data that will be collected includes [specific types of personal data, e.g., age, gender, occupation]. Your response or input is not just important; it's crucial for achieving the research project objectives, and we highly value your participation.

The survey also includes more general questions about environmental problems and concerns and trust in various actors in issues related to the extractive industry. In addition, the respondents are asked to write about their views on the future of their place of residence, their relationship with it, possible intentions to move, and the reasons affecting them.

The survey also contains map questions, where the respondents can mark on the map the areas for which they think the extractive industry's activities are suitable and the regions in which they would like to remain untouched. In addition, the survey collects background information about the respondents, such as age, education, industry, municipality of residence, and current postal/zip code.

The information is only used for research purposes and is not disclosed to actors outside the AGEMERA project. The data is also anonymised, so it is impossible to identify individual respondents.

Parties and division of responsibilities of the research collaboration

The University of Lapland and the project coordinator, the University of Oulu in Finland, designed the survey. As many AGEMERA project partners as possible should test it in different national contexts. The goal is to develop a survey tool (based on the comparison) that can also be used after the project. The original data is used only by the 'name of the partner organisation'.

The researcher responsible for the case study responsible for the further study

Add here the name of the responsible researcher for the questionnaire, address, phone number, and email address.

Contact information of the data protection officer

Inform previously about the questionnaire approach and privacy notice to the lawyer, legal advisor, and legal office from the local partner organisation and add the name and contact information of the legal person and responsible member from the local project partner here.

Name, type, and duration of the questionnaire survey

Name: Local people's perceptions of mineral exploration and mining in 'organisation name of the partner'.

Type: Quantitative research (questionnaire).

Duration: The questionnaire will be open from March 1st to May 15th, 2024. After that, the survey may be repeated before the end of the AGEMERA project (31.7.2025), a follow-up study. The material can be used in scientific articles, research reports, and theses during or after the project duration.

Legal basis for personal data processing

Performance of a task carried out in exercising official authority vested in the controller: scientific research.

Level of personal data collection and processing in the questionnaire survey

The questionnaire survey and research do not collect or discuss information about the respondents on an individual level. Background questions include the year of birth, gender, level of education, industry, municipality of residence, zip code of the apartment, length of time living in the municipality in years and the respondent's estimate of how long he/she thinks he/she will still live there. The themes of the other questions are described in the section 'Description of the research project and purpose of personal data processing'.

The survey collects both numerical and written information. Numerical data consists of answers given by respondents to question matrices and multiple-choice questions, and written data includes answers given by respondents to open questions.

Sensitive personal data

The survey does not ask for sensitive personal information (e.g., Racial or ethnic origins, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership,

genetic data, biometric data to uniquely identify a natural person, health, or sexual orientation).

Sources of personal data

All information is collected from the respondents themselves, and providing information is voluntary for the respondents.

Data transfer or disclosure outside the research group

The survey material will not be handed over to anyone.

Data transfer or disclosure outside the EU or the European Economic Area

Questionnaire data is not transferred or disclosed outside the EU or the European Economic Area.

Automated decisions

No automated decisions are made.

Safeguards to protect personal data

The collected data is confidential. The pseudonymised survey data will be stored on password—and username-protected computers and, if necessary, on backup encrypted hard drives and/or memory sticks. When data is exchanged between the researcher(s), for example, due to co-authorship or other reasons, it will always be anonymised. Direct identifiers are not collected during the questionnaire survey.

Processing of personal data after the end of the study

The questionnaire survey initiative ends on 31.7.2025, and at the same time, the AGEMERA project ends. After that, the safeguarded data will be saved for five years, and if the follow-up studies continue, the safeguarded data will be saved for five years after the study.

What rights do you have, and deviation from rights

The contact person in matters related to the subject's rights is the person mentioned in the Data Controller section of this notice.

Right to lodge a complaint

Anyone can file a complaint with the data protection commissioner's office/authority in their country if they believe that valid data protection legislation has been violated in processing their personal data. Add the authority and address to which the complaint should be sent.

This privacy notice is archived in the 'name of the partner organisation'.

2.4 Communication Strategies in Case Study Areas

This section outlines the communication strategies employed to distribute the questionnaire and engage local participants in Estonia, Germany, and Finland.

2.4.1 Estonia

In Estonia, the communication strategy for distributing the questionnaire was intentionally low-key due to the sensitive nature of the topic and the prevailing public sentiment. Unlike during the first campaign, when media attention escalated beyond control, no external media outreach was conducted this time. The national phosphate exploration project had recently gained momentum, prompting strong opposition from local communities. Given the heightened tensions, the project team at TalTech decided against a broad public campaign to avoid further controversy. Official letters containing the questionnaire link and background information were sent to municipalities, but these were not actively shared or promoted at the local level.

2.4.2 Germany

Following the initial launch of the questionnaire in the German case study area (Erzgebirge region, Saxony), it became evident that the collected responses mainly reflected input from specific population groups. This was likely influenced by the initial dissemination strategy, which relied on the communication channels of TUBAF, such as the university's website and social media platforms, as well as local media coverage including Radio Erzgebirge and the German Geological Society (DGGV). However, the results obtained still generated valuable, especially qualitative, insights into the local situation.

To address this and enhance the representativeness of the respondent base, the final survey launch was supported by a professional advertising agency. The agency leveraged regional online survey panels and targeted outreach methods to ensure broader dissemination. This expanded strategy enabled the inclusion of more diverse demographic, geographic, and social segments of the population, ultimately contributing to a more balanced and robust dataset for the project's analysis.

2.4.3 Finland

The follow-up survey for the residents of the municipalities of Rovaniemi, Posio and Kuusamo was open from 1 February to 9 March, 2025 in Webropol-survey platform. A link to the survey was stationed to the University of Lapland's webpage. The link to the survey was also marketed through local and national news media. News stories were published both in print and online. In addition, the survey was also marketed on social

media platforms. Based on the previous survey in 2023, a large number of people found the survey on social media. This was true also with this survey.

A few remarks are necessary regarding the implementation of the survey: (1) it is useful to continue monitoring the number of respondents throughout the survey. Once the response rate starts to dwindle, new marketing will be needed. (2) Despite the importance of social media, local and/or regional traditional media are important for marketing the survey. This involves reporting on the current content of the survey, highlighting the shortcomings of the survey or other activities. (3) In social media advertising, organisational advertising works best. If an individual researcher uses her/his own face/information to promote a survey, it can lead to long chains of interaction and even harassment.

Although the survey received a relatively large number of respondents, the data is not representative. Hence, the data cannot be generalized to represent the study region as a whole.

2.5 Overview of the Survey Results

The following section presents the survey results from Estonia, Germany, and Finland, offering a comparative overview of public perceptions, awareness levels, and attitudes toward mining and CRMs in each region. These results reflect data collected through the final questionnaire and provide insights into regional differences and common trends across the three case study areas.

2.5.1 Estonia

The survey conducted in Estonia yielded limited results, mainly due to the lack of an active communication campaign and low respondent engagement. In total, 48 individuals participated; however, as most questions in the questionnaire were optional, many responses were only partially completed (Table 1). This reduced the overall completeness and consistency of the dataset. The limited number of responses reflects the sensitivity of the topic and the prevailing public scepticism, especially in light of ongoing national discussions related to phosphate exploration. Given the small sample size and incomplete data, the results are not considered suitable for use in further analysis or comparative studies.

Table 1. Gender and socioeconomic status of survey respondents from the final questionnaire survey in Estonia.

		Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	20	41,6
	Male	19	39,6
	Other	9	18,8

Socioeconomic status	Employed	24	50
	Student	3	6,3
	Unemployed	4	8,3
	Retired	5	10,4
	Other	6	12,5
	Not Mentioned	6	12,5

2.5.2 Germany

The Erzgebirge region in the Free State of Saxony, located in eastern Germany, served as the primary focus for the re-launched questionnaire survey conducted within Germany. A total of 648 responses were collected through the LimeSurvey platform, comprising 413 complete and 235 partial responses. After performing data cleaning to ensure accuracy and consistency, 436 responses were deemed valid and suitable for further analysis.

Table 2 presents an overview of the demographic and socioeconomic profile of the respondents. A slightly higher proportion of participants identified as female (54.82%) compared to male (45.18%). In terms of socioeconomic status, the majority were employed (51.61%), followed by retired individuals (15.59%). Other categories included unemployed persons, homemakers, those in vocational training, students, self-employed individuals, civil servants, and others, providing a diverse representation of the regional population.

Table 2. Gender and Socioeconomic Status of Survey Respondents from the re-launch of the questionnaire survey in Germany.

		Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	54.82%
	Male	45.18%
Socioeconomic status	Retired	15.59%
	Employed	51.61%
	Unemployed	8.49%
	Homemaker	5.5%
	Self-employed	6.65%
	In vocational training	5.5%
	Student	3.21%
	Civil servant	1.15%
	Other	2.29%

2.5.3 Finland

A total of 851 people responded to the survey and out of 851 respondents, 841 indicated their municipality of residence. Of the respondents, 231 (27%) lived in Kuusamo, 66 (8%)

in Posio, and 284 (34%) in Rovaniemi. 260 respondents (31%) reported living elsewhere but are attached to one of the survey locations, for example through family roots, employment, or ownership of land or a cottage. The majority of those living elsewhere, 170 responses (65.4%), concerned Kuusamo. 56 responses (21.5%) concerned Posio and 33 responses (12.7%) concerned Rovaniemi.

The gender distribution of respondents was as follows: 434 women (51%), 387 men (46%), and four non-binary respondents (0.5%). Twenty-one respondents (2.5%) did not wish to answer the question about gender. The data has been presented in Table 3.

There were 71 respondents (9%) under the age of 35, 227 (27.5%) between the ages of 35 and 50, 296 (37.5%) between the ages of 51 and 65, and 205 (26%) over the age of 65. The average age of the respondents was 55.

Among those who responded to the survey, 26 (4%) reported that they are still in primary school or have completed basic education. A total of 327 respondents (39%) have completed upper secondary school or vocational education, and 484 (57%) have a higher education degree. The largest single educational background group is those with a master's degree from a university, which has 256 of respondents (30%).

There were 99 respondents (12%) working in managerial positions and 321 employees (38%). In addition, there were 124 entrepreneurs (15%), 30 unemployed (4%), 26 students (3%), and 217 retirees (26%). The three most common working life industries represented among respondents were public administration (111 respondents, 13%), teaching and education (104 respondents, 12%), and social and health services (89 respondents, 11%).

Table 3. Gender and Socioeconomic Status of Survey Respondents from the re-launch of the Questionnaire Survey in Finland. Total number of respondents: 851.

Category	Subgroup	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	51.0%
	Male	46.0%
	Non-binary	0.5%
	Prefer not to say	2.5%
Age Group	Under 35	9.0%
	35–50	27.5%
	51–65	37.5%
	Over 65	26.0%
Education Level	Basic education	4.0%
	Upper secondary / vocational	39.0%
	Higher education degree	57.0%
	— of which: Master's Degree	30.0%
Employment Status	Managerial position	12.0%
	Employee	38.0%

Entrepreneur	15.0%
Unemployed	4.0%
Student	3.0%
Retired	26.0%

The data was analysed municipality by municipality and taking into account both the responds of the locals and the responds of those, who have an attachment to the region. Hence, the total number of responses concerning Kuusamo is 401 (47.1% of the total), the total number of responses concerning Rovaniemi is 317 (37.3%) and the total number of responses concerning Posio is 122 (14.3%). The data analysis has been done based on these groups, with a primary focus on the municipalities of Kuusamo and Rovaniemi. The data from the municipality of Posio will be analysed in more depth at a later stage.

For the responses concerning Kuusamo, the respondents were on average slightly older than in Rovaniemi and Posio, as the average age in Kuusamo was 58 years. The average age in Posio was 55 years and the average age of respondents in Rovaniemi was 49.7 years.

For the responses concerning Rovaniemi, the respondents were more educated. In Rovaniemi, 73% of respondents had a higher education degree. In comparison, 48% of Kuusamo respondents and 49% of Posio respondents had a such degree.

In Rovaniemi, 71% of respondents were employed, in Kuusamo the share was 61% and in Posio 68%. The proportion of pensioners was 33% in Kuusamo, 27% in Posio and 17% in Rovaniemi.

Considering the gender of the respondents, in each municipality women were in the majority. Just over half of those who indicated their gender were female.

The analysis has focused on the survey item “I approve of mining in my region”. More than half of the respondents (54%) from Kuusamo strongly disagree and additionally 21% somewhat disagree with this statement.

The survey also included the statement: I hope that the exploration for ore will lead to the opening of a mine in Kuusamo, Posio or Rovaniemi. Here too, almost 70% (67.6%) of respondents from Kuusamo answered completely disagree. Opposition to ore exploration and mining is higher in Kuusamo than in the other survey municipalities. The same observation was also made in the survey conducted in 2023.

In Rovaniemi, 37% strongly disagree and 18% somewhat disagree with the statement “I accept mining in my home region. Slightly more than half (50.2%) of the respondents in Rovaniemi strongly disagreed with the statement “I hope that exploration will lead to the opening of a mine in Kuusamo, Posio or Rovaniemi”.

Based on the survey, the majority do not accept mining in their home region and the resistance is strong. However, the level of approval increases if the statement is about

mining in general. Similarly, mineral exploration is seen to be more acceptable than mining.

The respondents were divided into two groups, a) Mining critics, who somewhat disagree or strongly disagree with the statement “I accept mining in my home region” and b) Mining supporters, who somewhat agree or strongly agree with this statement.

Mining critics in Kuusamo include a total of 296 responses, or about 74% of the total. Mining critics in Rovaniemi include a total of 175 responses, or 55% of the responses.

Mining supporters in Kuusamo include a total of 90 responses, or 22% of the total. Mining supporters in Rovaniemi include a total of 128 responses, or 41% of the total.

In Rovaniemi, there is stronger support for mining among younger respondents. The strongest support was among those born between 1981 and 1990. Respondents under 40 years of age (81 respondents), 56% were in favour of mining. Of all the respondents over 40 years of age (192 respondents), 38% were in favour of mining. A clear increase in the number of approvers was noticed amongst those born after 1985.

Both in Kuusamo and Rovaniemi, the most trusted organizations by mining critics are environmental organizations and the scientific community. The weakest trust is in companies and decision-making, especially at the national level. There is little trust in the supervision of the authorities.

For supporters, trust in the scientific community is also strong. However, trust in regulatory supervision and mining companies is much stronger. Similarly, trust in the decision-making process and in companies is stronger than among critics. And then again: there is little trust in environmental organizations.

When examining trust in exploration companies and mining companies, it is largely influenced by the way these companies communicate with the local community. Almost 55% of the people in Kuusamo who responded to the survey have not been in touch with mining or mineral exploration companies. In the case of Rovaniemi, the proportion is almost 60%.

2.6 Comparison to the First Launch Questionnaire Survey

The results of the final questionnaire survey were compared to those from the initial launch to assess changes in public awareness, perceptions, and attitudes toward critical raw materials and mining activities. This comparative analysis aimed to identify shifts in understanding and engagement following educational and outreach efforts carried out during the project. The most notable differences between the two survey rounds are outlined below.

- Map-based elements were excluded from the final questionnaire due to technical limitations of the survey platforms employed, which did not support such functionalities. As a result, no map-based features were incorporated, and only the online questionnaire was distributed.
- In Finland, the number of respondents increased significantly: in 2023 there were just under 400 responses, compared to over 800 in 2025. This shows that people want to make their opinions heard and the survey is one way of doing this.

3 Launch of University Courses

In addition to assessing public awareness through surveys, another central aim of the project was to strengthen formal education on CRMs within higher education institutions. As future professionals and decision-makers will play a crucial role in enabling Europe's green and digital transition, it is essential that universities provide students with relevant and up-to-date knowledge on CRMs and their role in sustainable development. To address this need, two higher education activities were launched as part of the project. The first was the “European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)” course, implemented at TUBAF, and the second was a Micro-Degree programme titled “Sustainable Exploration, Mining and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources” offered at TalTech. Both initiatives were designed to promote interdisciplinary learning, raise awareness of CRM-related challenges and opportunities, and build capacity for innovation and sustainability in the raw materials sector.

3.1 European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs) – Course at TUBAF

This section provides an overview of the development and implementation of the “European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)” university course at TUBAF. It outlines the course's evolution from its initial launch to its re-establishment as a modular offering, highlighting key content, delivery formats, communication efforts, and student feedback. The section also presents performance assessments, identifies areas for improvement, and offers insights into the course's future development.

3.1.1 Summary of the First Launch of University Courses

Within this chapter a summary of the first launch of the courses is included for context. The first launch is described in detail in AGEMERA deliverable **D2.3 2nd year evaluation report on questionnaires, developed courses and events**.

To address the goals of task 2.3, ‘European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)’ was created, which is a series of online courses that were launched by the AGEMERA project. The ECRMs courses were designed to improve the understanding of critical raw materials (CRMs) and their importance in the context of the green and digital transition. These courses were developed in partnership with five higher education institutions, that are part of the AGEMERA Project: Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg (TUBAF), Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech), University of Oulu (OU), University of Lapland (UL) and University of Zambia in Zambia (UNZA).

The contents were made publicly available as part of the first launch for the first time on the OPAL online learning platform starting on March 4, 2024.

Initially designed for future engineers and scientists, the courses were structured to be accessible by anyone, regardless of their academic background or geographic location. They were offered online via the OPAL online platform, which features a modular design, intuitive navigation, and a system that distinguishes between student and tutor roles. Tutors had the ability to upload course content, while students could register, access materials, and submit assignments. Live lectures were conducted in virtual classrooms, with interactive features such as messaging, note sharing, and video interaction. All live sessions were recorded and uploaded to the VIMP video platform, with access links provided through OPAL.

The course materials were organized by chapters and lecture dates and included lecture files, literature and additional resources. Participants who completed a pre-examination and submitted feedback via an online questionnaire were awarded a Certificate of Attendance (COA). This certificate allowed them to proceed to a 90-minute online written exam, which, upon successful completion and enrolment at TUBAF, qualified them to receive three ECTS credits.

To promote the courses, a dedicated section was created on the AGEMERA website, which included registration guidance and highlighted course benefits such as learning flexibility, guest lectures, tutor support, certification, and the opportunity to earn ECTS credits. A media kit containing promotional visuals and text was developed and shared across digital platforms by GEO and participating universities. The promotional efforts reached thousands of users across Instagram, LinkedIn, Facebook, and X (formerly Twitter). Additional dissemination methods included email campaigns to students, in-person announcements, and listings in university publications like TUBAF's ProWissen booklet.

The content of the ECRMs courses was divided into seven main chapters and one bonus chapter. The main chapters covered topics such as geology and exploration of CRMs in Africa and Europe, exploration technologies, geopolitical challenges, global mining practices, social and environmental impact assessments, mineral economics, and international resource classification frameworks such as the United Nations Framework Classification (UNFC), Committee for Minerals Reserves International Reporting Standard (CRIRSCO) and the United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS). These topics were addressed through live online lectures held over nine days in March 2024. The bonus chapter included five additional presentations in April 2024, covering for example, muon-based rock density characterization, multi-sensing drones, or the OECD's Mining Regions and Cities Initiative.

The course assessment process involved a multiple-choice pre-examination, enabling automated evaluation and scalability. Participants needed to score at least 40% to pass and were allowed two retakes. Next to the pre-examination, a feedback questionnaire was used to collect data on participants' backgrounds, experiences, engagement, expectations, content evaluation, learning outcomes, marketing impact, and gave people the opportunity to leave comments on each answer provided. The feedback

indicated high levels of satisfaction with the course, its' structure, it was considered “easy access”, and contents were largely seen as new. Many respondents were postgraduate students at TUBAF, many studying a subject related to geosciences. The majority stated that the course met or exceeded their expectations and reported that their knowledge about CRMs was increased. Especially the technologies further developed and applied within the AGEMERA project, such as muography and drone-based surveys were considered interesting and novel to the participants.

Despite positive feedback, attendance at live sessions was modest, with only 35.6% average attendance for chapters 1 to 7 and about 10% for the bonus sessions. However, the recorded lectures accumulated over 650 views. This suggests that students actually took their time to re-watch the lectures, if they were not able to attend or use them to study for the examination.

When asked why students were unable to attend the live session, the most common reasons given were scheduling conflicts with work or other lectures.

The written examination was conducted online on May 3, 2024, with strict identification and technical requirements. Nineteen participants registered and all successfully passed the exam.

Key recommendations for the future included eliminating the bonus chapter and instead integrating its content into the curriculum, which is mandatory for performance assessments. Further suggestions involved aligning course schedules with partner university timetables, introducing hybrid learning formats, and incorporating case studies to enhance engagement. The feedback also emphasized the importance of using internal university communication channels, rather than general social media, to more effectively reach students.

The pilot phase confirmed the program's effectiveness in advancing CRM education. It successfully addressed a knowledge gap in digitally available resources on CRMs across more than 25 countries. Feedback strongly supported the continuation and expansion of the ECRMs initiative, highlighting particular interest in the novel technologies and international frameworks covered.

3.1.2 Establishment of ECRMs as a Module / Micro-Credential

The faculty board of the *Faculty of Geosciences, Geoengineering and Mining* at TUBAF officially agreed to include ECRMs as a module on February 13, 2024. However, the courses were designed as a micro-credential and always titled as such. Through discussions with TUBAF's administrative staff and student office, several key topics related to micro-credentials were addressed. A central point of discussion was the integration of micro-credentials into TUBAF's academic and administrative systems. In this context, the AGEMERA micro-credential appears to have triggered a broader administrative process. The engagement of TUBAF's AGEMERA project members

seemingly contributed to the progress toward the formal recognition of micro-credentials within the university and has helped pave the way for similar initiatives. On June 13, 2024, TUBAF officially published the new regulation on micro-credentials.

3.1.3 Re-Launch of the University Courses

With potential tendencies for improvements in mind from the first launch, ECRMs was re-launched in the winter semester, starting on October 15, 2024. Changes included the establishment of hybrid courses at TUBAF, and bonus content was made mandatory.

3.1.4 Hybrid Courses at TUBAF

Figure 2. Seminar room used for conducting hybrid courses at TUBAF

In the first launch of the courses, out of 33 respondents, that provided feedback, 24.24% strongly agreed that participants have the opportunity to engage with other people in the online course, while 18.18% agreed and 45.45% were neutral. Given the high proportion of neutral responses, TUBAF introduced hybrid course formats to enhance the overall learning experience, with a particular focus on increasing student engagement.

A seminar room at TUBAF was made available for students who wished to attend the lectures in person (Figure 2). Simultaneously, all lectures were broadcast live via the virtual classroom on Opal. When external lecturers delivered sessions, students could gather in the seminar room to participate together in a shared learning environment. When lecturers from TUBAF presented, they did so directly from the seminar room, with the lecture live streamed to the virtual classroom. This setup was designed to better respond to feedback and enhance opportunities for student engagement.

3.1.5 Presented Contents

Table 4. Contents of the re-launched ECRMs courses

Date of Presentation	Title of the Lecture
Tuesday, October 15, 2024	Geology of REEs and BRMs in Africa (Zambia) & Conventional Exploration Technologies for CRMs
Monday, October 21, 2024	Geology of REEs and BRMs in Europe
Tuesday, November 5, 2024	Muon-Based Density Characterization of Rocks (by Muon Solutions)
Monday, November 11, 2024	Drone-based EM survey system Geology & Exploration of CRMs (by Radai)
Monday, November 18, 2024	Data Visualisation Technologies (by OPT/NET)
Monday, December 2, 2024	The Green New Deal & CRMs Part 1
Tuesday, December 3, 2024	The Green New Deal & CRMs Part 2
Monday, January 13, 2025	CRMs in a Global Environment
Monday, January 20, 2025	SDGs, UNFC and UNRMS
Monday, January 27, 2025	Environmental Impact Assessment in the Extractive Sector
Monday, February 3, 2025	Social Assessment in Mining and Exploration
Friday, February 7, 2025	Economic Resource Evaluation

The contents presented largely followed the structure of the initial launch. However, presentations that were previously part of the bonus chapter were integrated into the mandatory section, as participants found the materials interesting and attendance for bonus lectures was noticeably lower than for mandatory sessions. The contents were refined and updated by the presenters.

3.1.6 TUBAF

A specific section was created during the first launch of the courses on the AGEMERA website to promote and disseminate information about the university courses designed for the AGEMERA project. This section has since been updated and offers a comprehensive overview of the relevant information involved. The courses were also promoted on a dedicated AGEMERA section of TUBAF's own website, where all project-related topics are being presented.

The courses were promoted through TUBAF's social media channels Instagram and Facebook. Approximately 2,300 people were reached on Instagram, while on Facebook around 3,200 impressions were achieved.

and a visual invitation to enrol was displayed on all digital screens installed across the university, as displayed in Figure 3.

YOU WANT TO LEARN MORE ABOUT CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS?

Join the course on Opal:

European Critical Raw Materials for the
Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)

✓ 3 ECTS credits

✓ Certification
of attendance

✓ Hybrid: Online & in
presence (UBH-0208)

Scan me for more info!

European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)

Brought to you by the Horizon Europe project AGEMERA (grant agreement no. 101058178)

Figure 3. Course advertisement shared on TUBAF's digital screens installed across the university campus

In addition, the poster previously prepared in cooperation with GEO for the first launch was updated and displayed in the University's canteen to attract students and the entrance of the Chair for Underground Mining Methods.

3.1.7 Performance Assessments, Feedback Received & Certification of Attendance

As in the initial course launch, an online pre-examination was conducted to assess participants' readiness for the 90-minute, online, graded written examination. Passing this pre-examination remained a mandatory requirement to qualify for the final assessment. Participants who successfully completed the pre-examination and submitted feedback via an online questionnaire received a Certificate of Attendance (COA). Obtaining the COA and registering at TUBAF as either a guest auditor or a regular student was a prerequisite for participating in the final written examination.

The structure of the pre-examination in this launch was largely similar to the original version, consisting of 31 multiple-choice questions instead of the initial 33. Two questions were removed due to updates in course content. Each correctly answered question was worth one point. The questions were developed in collaboration with representatives from the partner higher education institutions (HEIs) and were based on material from all seven course chapters. The multiple-choice format was selected to allow for automatic evaluation through the OPAL system, which does not support qualitative

assessments. This approach ensures scalability and significantly reduces administrative workload.

A total of eight participants completed the pre-examination during this phase. The average score achieved was 25.62 out of 31, equating to approximately 82.65%. Participants who do not pass the pre-examination are generally allowed up to two additional attempts to meet the passing requirements.

To gather feedback and evaluate whether the course achieved its objective of increasing participants' understanding of the significance of CRMs, an online questionnaire was once again provided via OPAL. The structure and contents of the questionnaire remained unchanged and can be observed in AGEMERA D 2.3.

3.1.8 Results from the Feedback Questionnaire

▪ Topic 1 Background Information About Participants

A total of participants from seven different countries, including Germany, Nigeria, Pakistan, Finland, and Croatia, took part in the feedback questionnaire. Of these, 75% indicated they are currently enrolled at a HEI, while 25% were not. The enrolled students were affiliated with institutions such as TUBAF, the University of Helsinki, the University of Oulu, and the University of Zagreb. They were studying programs including *Sustainable Mining and Remediation Management* and *Geological Engineering*. Approximately 42.86% were enrolled in a master's program, 28.57% in a bachelor's program, and 14.29% in a doctoral program. Most respondents (66.67%) were midway through their studies, while 16.67% had just started and another 16.67% were nearing completion.

▪ Topic 2 Course Experience

Regarding the course experience, 75% of participants agreed or strongly agreed that registration was easy, while 12.5% disagreed. All respondents found the course easy to navigate, indicated by selecting either “strongly agree” or “agree”. When asked whether they would consider attending a similar course in the future, all participants responded positively, selecting either “very likely” or “likely”. Online and hybrid lecture formats were the most preferred among respondents, receiving the highest ratings as the favoured modes of course delivery. One participant remarked: “Virtual classrooms are very important and help bridge the distance gap, while physical sessions support interpersonal relationships and interaction with fellow students and teachers”. In terms of attendance, 50% of respondents reported attending more than 76% of the live sessions covering the mandatory content (Chapters 1 to 7), while 25% indicated they attended 50% or fewer of the presentations.

▪ **Topic 3: Participant Engagement**

Half of the participants felt neutral about the opportunities to engage with others, while 50% agreed or strongly agreed that such opportunities were present. The tutors received strong positive feedback, with 87.5% indicating they were open to engagement and 87.5% rating them as competent as well, by either selecting “strongly agree” or “agree”. One person thanked the tutors for being always open to questions and helping students.

▪ **Topic 4 Course Motivation and Expectations**

The reasons for attending the course included academic relevance, interest in CRMs, and professional development. Participants highlighted a desire to learn about critical raw materials in relation to sustainability, policy, and global challenges. All respondents confirmed that the course met their expectations, with 75% strongly agreeing and the remaining 25% agreeing. Responses from participants included:

- “I attend the course because I'm really interested into mineral deposits and problem about critical minerals. I wanted to learn more about them and how important they are for the people, economy and situation in the world. From the geological side I wanted to learn more about them because I think they are very important to us and that hear some ideas and to get some knowledge about them can be a good thing for the future.”
- “My colleague send me [*sic*] an advertisement email of the course, and I got interested. I find the theme of the course very topical and I wanted to learn about the CRMs, "clean energy" and the controversies/challenges related to that.”
- “This course has a lot to do with my current studies and also the content of the course is really interesting.”
- “I really enjoyed the course and learned a lot! Thank you!”

▪ **Topic 5 Content Evaluation**

The feedback questionnaire also assessed participants' interest in the contents of the courses. Overall, the responses reflect a high level of interest in the materials presented.

The participants of the feedback questionnaire were asked to rate how interesting they found each lecture. The sessions on Geology of CRMs in Africa and Geology of CRMs in Europe received the strongest responses, with 71.43% of participants rating both as “most interesting” and the remaining 28.57% as “interesting.” Other presentations that stood out included Mining in a Global Environment (57.14% “most interesting”) and The Green New Deal & CRMs (71.43% “interesting”).

Emerging technologies introduced in the course were also well received. The lecture on Muon-Based Density Characterization of Rocks was rated as “most interesting” by

42.86% and “interesting” by 28.57%. The session on Multi-Sensing Drones elicited a mixed response: while 42.86% found it “most interesting,” another 42.86% selected “neutral,” which may suggest either varying levels of familiarity with the topic or differences in background knowledge.

Participants were asked how novel the contents were in comparison to their existing knowledge. The course was largely successful in presenting new material: 71.43% indicated that the lecture on CRMs in Africa contained a majority of new content, and 42.86% described the session on Muon-Based Characterization as “completely new.” Similarly, the AGEMERA Graphical User Interface was new to all participants, with 57.14% rating it as “completely new” and 42.86% as “mostly new.”

These results indicate that the course effectively introduced participants to both foundational and advanced topics, balancing well-known geological content with innovative technologies and international frameworks. This blend appears to have been particularly effective in keeping the course relevant and engaging for a diverse group of learners.

▪ **Topic 6 Learning Outcomes**

According to the responses, 50% of participants were introduced to CRMs for the first time during the course, while the other half already had prior exposure. Nevertheless, all respondents agreed that the course enhanced their understanding across various topics related to CRMs. When asked how else the course contributed to their knowledge of CRMs, participants provided the following selected responses:

- “This course improved my knowledge because it explained more about them. Unfortunately, we don’t talk about them specifically on college because I’m still on bachelor’s degree [*sic*] and we still learn more about general geology. But this course really explained the whole process about critical raw materials, where they can be found, on which way, how that affect [*sic*] on the environment and people and everything else about them.”
- “The course has introduced a lot of knowledge regarding the effects of CRMs in our life as well different aspects of CRMs like geopolitics and geology.”
- “Understanding and usage, environmental impacts, social norms, and future impacts”

▪ **Topic 7 Marketing Data Collection**

Participants reported hearing about the course through a range of sources, including university mailing lists, LinkedIn posts, faculty announcements, and recommendations from colleagues or friends. Notably, all respondents stated they would have attended the course even without the incentive of ECTS credits, indicating strong intrinsic motivation and interest in the subject matter.

- **Topic 8 Survey Conclusion**

In the final section of the questionnaire, participants were invited to share any additional remarks or comments. The majority chose not to respond.

- **Online Written Examination**

The procedure for participating in the online written examination followed the same approach as described in D 2.3. New questions were developed in close collaboration with the guest lecturers, while the number of questions and the overall workload were comparable to those of the examination conducted in the first launch of the courses. The examination was conducted online on March 11, 2025. Four participants took part, all of whom successfully passed and were awarded a second certificate by TUBAF. This certificate verifies their eligibility to claim 3 ECTS credits.

3.1.9 Key Outcomes

The re-launch of the university course series of ECRMs successfully built upon the foundations laid during the initial course offering in early 2024. The updated course structure integrated bonus content directly into the main curriculum and introduced hybrid learning opportunities at TUBAF to improve student engagement. Participant feedback remained largely positive, with high levels of satisfaction regarding course navigation, content novelty, tutor performance, and perceived learning gains regarding CRMs.

The online pre-examination demonstrated consistent performance, with an average score of 82.65%, reflecting strong comprehension of the presented materials. All participants who attended the online written examination passed, underlining the effectiveness of the course in preparing learners for a final assessment. Notably, the written feedback emphasized the value of the presented contents, particularly the sessions on muography, drone-based surveys, and international frameworks like UNFC and UNRMS, as well as the perceived accessibility of the course to a wide audience.

3.1.10 Improvement Scope

Compared to the first launch, overall participation numbers were lower in the second round, resulting in fewer students completing the pre-examination, feedback questionnaire, and final written exam. This drop may be partially explained by a saturation effect, as the course was offered again directly in the following semester after its debut in early 2024. With a large share of participants affiliated with TUBAF, it is likely that much of the initial target audience has already been reached. Going forward, it will be interesting to monitor participation trends over time to assess how enrolment to ECRMs develops across multiple semesters and institutions.

3.1.11 Outlook

The re-launch of the ECRMs university courses successfully built on the initial implementation by incorporating previously optional content into the core curriculum and introducing hybrid formats at TUBAF. These improvements directly addressed earlier feedback and contributed to a consistently positive learning experience, with participants expressing satisfaction regarding content quality, relevance, tutor engagement, and accessibility.

The course series has proven to be a valuable, scalable, and interdisciplinary educational offering that fills a critical gap in sustainable resource education. Its recognition as a micro-credential at TUBAF and flexible digital format support ongoing integration into academic programs and broader adoption across the AGEMERA network.

3.2 Sustainable Exploration, Mining and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources – Micro-Degree at TalTech

TalTech’s micro-degree “Sustainable Exploration, Mining and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources” comprises of two 6 ECTS modules delivered via TalTech’s Moodle platform. The two modules are – Mining in a Global Environment, and Circular Economy for Materials Processing. The micro-degree has been delivered **twice since its launch in September 2024** and is **planned to continue** with the next session running from **September 1, 2025, to January 25, 2026**. As of July 28, 2025, a total of 62 participants have already registered, the majority based in Africa.

The target audience is master's students and industry professionals in mining, geology, environmental and natural sciences, policymakers and stakeholders interested in sustainable raw materials across the EU and beyond.

The course aims to deepen understanding of mining worldwide by exploring its **environmental, economic, social, and political** dimensions. Topics include mining governance and regulation, financing, health and safety, the transformative role of mining firms, cross-cultural management, gender equity, artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM), Indigenous rights, community engagement, the “resource curse,” and climate change impacts. It also surveys cutting-edge techniques in mineral exploration. A further objective is to introduce **circular economy principles** and **resource efficiency** strategies, equipping participants with practical skills to apply sustainable processes across the mining and raw material value chain.

3.2.1 Content and Structure of the Micro-Degree

The micro-degree is structured as a comprehensive 12 ECTS programme designed for working professionals, students and a wide range of stakeholders globally. The programme is delivered over approximately 2–3 semesters via online and hybrid formats. It consists of two core modules: Mining in a Global Environment and Circular

Economy for Materials Processing. The former module consists of a weekly series of lectures presented live but also recorded for participants that cannot attend online delivery. The latter module consists of a series of themes that students can access anytime that fits with their schedule. The titles of the lectures and themes are outlined in Table 5 and Table 6.

Course “Mining in a Global Environment” Core Themes:

- **Global mining industry overview:** Governance, regulation, financing, health and safety, geopolitics, supply and value chains.
- **Strategic and Security Considerations:** Minerals considered strategic play a critical role in defence and technology sectors.
- **Sustainable Development:** Contribution towards sustainable development: providing the materials needed for infrastructure development, economic growth, and improving living standards. The UN SDGs are presented here.
- **Social dimensions:** Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Environmental and Social Governance (ESG) requirements, Indigenous rights, gender equality, community engagement, the resource curse and artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM).
- **Environmental & climate considerations:** Impact of climate change on mining zones. EU directives including Extractive Waste, Waste Framework, Water & Groundwater Directives, Birds Directive, Habitats Directive and Nature Directive (Natura 2000).
- **The Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA)** How the extractive sector will adopt the CRMA as part of the Green Deal. Challenges and opportunities are examined under the CRMA.
- **Technological innovations:** Emerging exploration tools and practices, innovative exploration technologies that are cost effective and non-invasive. These lectures concentrate on AGEMERA’s exploration technology partners that feature passive Seismic Methods, Multi-Sensor Drone Systems, Muon-Based Multidetector (Muon Imaging / Muography) and AI & Machine Learning. These platforms are presented in video format for greater understanding.

The lecture content covers a broad range of topics, including an introduction to mining in a global context, environmental and social challenges, sustainable mining practices, corporate social responsibility, health and safety management, and environmental impact assessment in the extractive sector, as well as presentations from AGEMERA partners such as Radaí OY, LITHICA, Muon Solutions, and OPT/NET, along with a dedicated session on artisanal mining (Table 5).

Table 5. Lecture content for “Mining in a Global Environment”.

Lecture no.	Lecture Title
Lecture 1	Introduction to Mining in a Global Environment
Lecture 2	Environmental and Social Challenges
Lecture 3	Sustainable Mining Practices - An Environmentally Responsible Approach
Lecture 4	Corporate Social Responsibility in mining
Lecture 5	Health And Safety Management in Mining
Lecture 6	AGEMERA Partner Radai OY
Lecture 7	AGEMERA Partner LITHICA
Lecture 8	AGEMERA Partner Muon Solutions
Lecture 9	AGEMERA Partner OPT/NET
Lecture 10	Environmental Impact Assessment in the Extractive Sector
Lecture 11	Artisanal Mining

The second course, “Circular Economy for Materials Processing”, focuses on the following core themes:

- **Mapping the full materials value chain:** Exploration → mining → processing → manufacturing → end-of-life recycling and reuse.
- **Fundamentals of circular economy & resource efficiency:** Foundational concepts, material flows, impacts, and drivers for change.
- **Sustainability impact assessment:** Understanding environmental, economic, and social effects of materials processing.
- **Technologies for sustainable processing:** Resource-efficient methods and recycling technologies for metals, polymers, glass and ceramics.
- **Circular business and innovation models:** Value chain stakeholders, business opportunities, entrepreneurship within circular frameworks.
- **Lifecycle-focused product design:** Strategies for long-lasting, repairable, and recyclable products.

The course content is structured around key thematic areas, beginning with an introduction to the course framework and the UN SDGs, followed by in-depth exploration of circular economy concepts, material resources, the environmental impact of exploration and mining, material processing and reprocessing, sustainable manufacturing and use-phase considerations, and concluding with recycling and reuse practices, including those related to ceramics and metals (Table 6).

Table 6. Theme content for “Circular Economy for Materials Processing”.

Course Themes	Title
Course introduction	The course introduction – content, evaluation criteria, course organisation. Sustainable Development Goals – the blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future.
Theme 1	Concept of circular economy and sustainable development
Theme 2	Materials and available resources
Theme 3	Exploration and impact and mining plus impact (metals and minerals)
Theme 4	Processing and re-processing of materials
Theme 5	Manufacturing (design) and use-phase
Theme 6	Recycling and re-use (including ceramics and metals)

3.2.2 Key Outcomes

The Micro-Degree programme “Sustainable Exploration, Mining and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources” at TalTech equips participants with a comprehensive understanding of the entire materials value chain, viewed through the lens of resource efficiency and sustainability. A central outcome is the development of a holistic perspective on the global mining industry, integrating environmental, economic, social, and political dimensions. Students gain a clear understanding of the importance of the extractive sector and its role in supporting modern society. The programme also introduces cutting-edge exploration technologies such as passive seismic methods, drone-based sensing, and muon imaging, giving learners practical insight into innovation in the field. In addition, participants master key principles of the circular economy, including material flow analysis and sustainable resource management. They develop the ability to explain and apply circular practices, such as recycling, sustainable processing, and resource re-entry strategies. The programme also fosters entrepreneurial thinking by highlighting business opportunities in circular systems and encouraging students to identify innovative pathways for reintroducing materials into new and existing value chains.

3.2.3 Communication & Dissemination

Communication and dissemination of the course was carried out through multiple channels, including the official TalTech website, the Department of Geology’s webpage, and various social media platforms. A significant number of students learned about the course through LinkedIn, where targeted posts, particularly on the AGEMERA LinkedIn page, and sponsored online advertisements played a key role in outreach and visibility

(see Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6). These efforts ensured broad reach across both academic and professional networks, attracting a diverse group of participants interested in raw materials, sustainability, and circular economy topics.

The screenshot shows the TalTech website header with navigation links: Admissions, Student, Research, Cooperation, and About the University. The course title is prominently displayed in bold, followed by the dates 02.09.2024–26.01.2025. Below the title, it indicates the location (Moodle), credits (12 EAP), and language (English). There are two main buttons: 'ENROLL' and 'MAKE INQUIRY', along with links to add the course to an iCal or Google Calendar.

Figure 4. Registration link for the course on TalTech homepage.

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn profile for the Department of Geology | TalTech, which has 735 followers and was last edited 10 months ago. The main post is a announcement for a Micro degree in "Sustainable Exploration, Mining, and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources" (12EAP, 02.09.2024-26.01.2025). The post text states: "The aim of the course is to emphasise the #environmental, economic, social, and political aspects of mining activities worldwide, enhancing knowledge of the global #mining industry." Below this, there is a list of details: Language: English; Price comment: Free of charge for participants; Prerequisites: BSc / Motivation letter by e-mail to Karin Robam at karin.robam@taltech.ee (By August 20th 2024).

Figure 5. Information and registration link for the course on Department of Geology, TalTech LinkedIn page.

Figure 6. Information and registration link for the course on AGEMERA's LinkedIn page.

3.2.4 Participant numbers

The micro-degree programme has attracted 85 participants so far, reflecting strong interest in the subject matter. Of these, 29 successfully completed both modules and received certification demonstrating the programme's value for committed learners.

While the overall completion rate was modest, it offers insight into potential areas for improvement. The lack of a financial commitment, given the programme's free offering, may have influenced motivation levels, while competing academic or work obligations likely affected sustained engagement. Without direct feedback from non-completers, the precise reasons remain unclear.

Notably, participants who actively engaged with the course maintained strong attendance and completed the programme, indicating that the structure and delivery were effective. Future iterations may benefit from strengthened support and engagement strategies to boost retention and learner outcomes.

3.2.5 Performance Assessments & Certification of Attendance

Performance in the Micro-Degree programme was evaluated through a combination of assessment tools tailored to each course component.

In the "Mining in a Global Environment" course, students were assessed through written assignments, reflective essays, and a final examination, which collectively measured their understanding of the mining sector's global and interdisciplinary dimensions.

In the "Circular Economy for Materials Processing" course, six short thematic tests were used to assess core knowledge, complemented by a final project in which students applied circular economy principles to real-world scenarios.

These assessment methods ensured both theoretical comprehension and practical application. Upon successful completion of all course requirements, participants received an official certificate of attendance, confirming their achievements in the programme (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Certificate of completion by TalTech.

3.2.6 Feedback Received

Participant feedback emphasised appreciation for the self-paced learning format, the clear and logical course structure, and the high quality of the instructional materials. Feedback was collected through multiple channels, including a dedicated feedback section within Moodle, where students could share comments and suggestions. Additional input was received via direct email correspondence with course instructors. Moreover, self-reflective essays proved to be a valuable tool for instructors to assess

participants' learning progress and gain deeper insight into their engagement with the course content.

Quizzes, assignments, and practical examples are seen as valuable tools that support effective learning and skill acquisition. The free access to the course and the option to select the final assignment contributed positively to the learner's experience for the Circular Economy for Materials Processing course. The assignments for Mining in a Global Environment also allowed the student to select the subject of their choice.

The e-support, including timely availability of resources on Moodle and active discussion forums, enhanced engagement and facilitated knowledge sharing. Suggestions for improvement focused on earlier access to lecture materials, more practical and interactive content, and increased student involvement. Some learners expressed a desire to apply theoretical knowledge more directly through hands-on projects and case studies to deepen their practical understanding. Although a few participants experienced minor technical difficulties and initial uncertainties about the course format, overall feedback was very positive, demonstrating the course's effectiveness as a micro-degree for professional development and lifelong learning.

An unexpected but encouraging source of feedback emerged through student activity on LinkedIn. Upon successfully completing the micro-degree, several participants updated their profiles to showcase their new qualification. This organic promotion appears to have sparked increased interest in the course – particularly among their professional networks – as reflected in the current registration of 37 participants (as of 10 July 2025) for the forthcoming delivery in the autumn semester 2025.

Insights like this will be valuable in shaping future iterations of the programme, particularly in enhancing outreach and engagement strategies.

3.2.7 Improvement Scope

Understanding the factors behind student disengagement is essential for enhancing the future delivery of the micro-degree. The following considerations may help address this challenge and support improved learner retention.

- **Advertising and Dissemination:** Reach target audiences with a clear value proposition, using digital channels—particularly LinkedIn—and strong calls to action. Continuously monitor and adjust strategies based on performance insights.
- **Modular & Flexible Design:** Transform the course into shorter, stackable credentials that fit within one or two semesters and align with professionals' schedules.
- **Enhanced Recognition:** Strengthen accreditation and integration with EU-wide micro-credential frameworks to boost credibility and facilitate credit transfer.

- **Digital & Pedagogical Upgrades:** Expand the use of hybrid delivery, interactive learning tools, and AI-assisted content to foster engagement and adaptability.
- **Industry-Driven Updates:** Collaborate with employers to keep the curriculum current with emerging technologies and workplace needs. Inviting speakers from industry will be used for future delivery of the courses.
- **Upskilling Pathways:** Embed the micro-degree within broader lifelong learning routes, supporting ongoing professional development in green and digital sectors.

3.2.8 Outlook

The following outlook outlines strategic vision for the future development and enhancement of the micro-degree, focusing on innovation, relevance, and expanding opportunities for learners in emerging fields.

- **Competitive Positioning:** Establish TalTech as a frontrunner in offering agile, career-focused credentials that remain relevant in a rapidly changing job market.
- **Stackable Credential Pathways:** Allow learners to accumulate multiple micro-credentials toward broader qualifications and cohesive learning tracks.
- **Green & AI Integration:** Introduce modules on artificial intelligence and green technologies to prepare learners for digital transformation and sustainability challenges.
- **Immersive & Personalised Learning:** Leverage VR/AR, simulations, and gamification for deeper learner engagement and customized educational experiences.
- **Strategic Scaling:** Grow connections with employers, government bodies, and international education partners to expand course offerings into other high-demand fields.

3.2.9 Summary

TalTech's AGEMERA micro-degree exemplifies flexibility, quality, and digital innovation, offering a future-ready qualification tailored for lifelong learners in sustainability, the circular economy, and digital transformation. Designed with strong industry relevance, the programme equips graduates with in-demand skills for emerging roles in recycling, resource-efficient processing, ESG consulting, environmental engineering, and sustainable mining – fields central to Europe's green transition. The micro-degree not only prepares individuals for impactful green careers but also contributes to the revitalisation of the mining sector by attracting fresh talent into a high-tech,

environmentally responsible industry. Its recognition for credit mobility and professional credibility across the EU and beyond further enhances its long-term value.

While learner interest has been encouraging, the experience also highlights key engagement challenges common to free or low-cost programmes. Ensuring high completion rates will require ongoing investment in learner support, structured mentorship, and flexible delivery methods. Addressing barriers such as time constraints, varying levels of digital readiness, and the need for sustained motivation will be essential to fostering both enrolment and successful completion in future cohorts.

4 Communicating Critical Raw Materials: Events and Digital Outreach

Alongside its research and innovation efforts, AGEMERA places strong emphasis on public awareness and open dialogue surrounding the exploration and extraction of CRMs. Recognising that societal acceptance is vital for the long-term success of CRM-related activities, the project engaged a wide range of stakeholders through educational materials, surveys, interviews, and public events. These initiatives brought together citizens, businesses, NGOs, policymakers, and regulatory authorities – both those directly impacted by mining and those involved in shaping related policies.

Public-facing activities such as workshops, seminars, and community events were carried out to enhance understanding of CRMs and their role in the green and digital transition. Organised by the **Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg, University of Oulu, University of Lapland, Tallinn University of Technology, University of Zambia, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences**, and with support from AGEMERA's Dissemination and Communication Leader, Hungarian SME Geonardo Environmental Technologies (GEONARDO), these events addressed key themes, reached diverse audiences, and applied targeted engagement strategies. Insights from pre- and post-event surveys offer a valuable look into evolving public perceptions, knowledge levels, and interest in CRM-related topics.

4.1 Workshops, Seminars and Public Events

Workshops, seminars, and broader public events formed a key part of AGEMERA's approach to engaging communities on the societal, environmental, and economic dimensions of CRMs. These events aimed to highlight the relevance of CRMs in everyday life, their importance to sustainable development, and their role in securing Europe's green and digital future. Designed to be inclusive and accessible, the activities reached a diverse audience – including students, educators, residents, and industry stakeholders – while fostering meaningful dialogue and critical reflection.

To assess the impact of these outreach efforts, participants were invited to complete pre- and post-event surveys. These provided insight into changes in awareness, understanding, and attitudes, offering valuable feedback to guide future engagement activities. Events took a range of formats, from interactive workshops and panel discussions to public lectures and exhibitions and were delivered across multiple countries by AGEMERA partners. Activities were adapted to local contexts to ensure cultural and regional relevance. In addition to national-level efforts, AGEMERA also contributed to awareness-raising at major European conferences and cluster events, expanding its reach to international audiences and strengthening visibility in the raw materials and policy communities.

A total of 20 events were organised by AGEMERA partners across six countries – Finland, Estonia, Italy, Germany, Bulgaria, and Zambia. These included public events, workshops, and seminars. The activities engaged a wide range of target groups, from civil society and students to industry representatives and educators. Altogether, the events reached **1635 participants**. A full overview of events, including locations, formats, and participant data, is provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Workshops, Seminars and Public Events from July 2024 to July 2025.

Date	Type	Involved Partner	Venue/ Place	Covered Topics	Target Group	Participants
29.09. 2024	Public event	OU, TT	Oulu, Finland	Raising awareness of CRMs through various hands-on activities	Civil Society	400
10.10. 2024	Public event	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	AGEMERA Project, importance of CRM	Civil Society	38
21.11. 2024	Public event	TT	Bologna, Italy	To raise awareness of CRM for high school	Civil Society	48
05.12. 2024	Seminar	TT	Online	Webinar for teachers to introduce the topic of CRM and workshop	Civil Society	9
25.02. 2025	Workshop	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	Workshop "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Citizens	15
27.02. 2025	Workshop	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	Introduction AGEMERA Workshop "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Civil Society	13
03.03. 2025	Workshop	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Civil Society	9
05.03. 2025	Public event	TUBAF	Freiberg, Germany	A dialogue on critical raw	Civil Society	100

				material mining in Erzgebirge with industry and authorities		
15.03. 2025	Workshop	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Citizens	22
08.04. 2025	Workshop	TT	Tartu, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Citizens	99
09.04. 2025	Workshop	TT	Tartu, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through various hands-on activities	Civil Society	200
22.04. 2025	Public event	BAS	Sofia, Bulgaria	AGEMERA project and the importance of the CRM in our all-day life	Civil Society	100
25.04. 2025	Workshop	TT	Pärnu, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Citizens	32
06.05. 2025	Seminar	TT, OU	Tallinn, Estonia	AGEMERA project's achievements and fostered dialogue on the future of critical raw materials and technological innovation in the mining sector.	Industry, business partners	60
10.- 11.05. 2025	Public event	BAS	Sofia, Bulgaria	Raising awareness of CRMs through various hands-on activities	Civil Society	300

22.05.2025	Public event	UL, OU	Rovaniemi, Finland	Discussion about mineral exploration and mining	Citizens	46
02.06.2025	Workshop	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Citizens	41
04.06.2025	Workshop	TT	Sindi, Estonia	Raising awareness of CRMs through "Where Does the Fork Come From?"	Citizens	36
05.06.2025	Public event	UL, OU	Kuusamo, Finland	Discussion about mineral exploration and mining	Citizens	39
05.06.2025	Seminar	TT	Tallinn, Estonia	Introduction AGEMERA online CRM game	Civil Society	5
13.06.2025	Seminar	UNZA, UO	Lusaka, Zambia	AGEMERA Final Results Showcase: Innovation, Impact & Zambia-Europe Collaboration for Sustainable Critical Raw Materials Development	Industry, business partners	65

4.1.1 Germany

On 5 March 2025, AGEMERA via its partner TUBAF hosted a public discussion in Freiberg, a German town that is part of the UNESCO World Heritage Site "Erzgebirge/Krušnohoří Mining Region" which attracted almost 100 participants. Among the participants were representatives from mining companies, the regional mining authority, environmental protection organisations, students, and citizens with a general interest in the subject.

Following a brief welcome speech, a representative from TUBAF delivered a presentation providing context on the political background of the Paris Agreement, the European Green Deal, and the Critical Raw Materials Act. The aim was to help the audience understand the relevance of these frameworks for current raw material

initiatives, considering the following discussion. The presentation addressed the growing demand for raw materials essential to the digital and green transitions, explained what critical raw materials are, why they matter, and how the AGEMERA project contributes to this broader context. Following that, mining companies currently developing their projects in the Erzgebirge Region presented the progress on their projects. Afterwards, the mining authority shared insights from past public events and dialogues with stakeholders. After these presentations, attendees had the opportunity to voice their opinions, ask questions and engage directly with mining companies, the mining authority and fellow participants. This exchange evolved into a dynamic discussion. Towards the end of the event, guests were invited to continue their conversations in a relaxed setting over complimentary snacks and drinks.

The event served as a neutral platform for open discourse, allowing different attendees to share their perspectives, address concerns and contribute to a constructive dialogue on how the future of critical raw materials in the region could look like under the consideration of stakeholder needs. The event was well received, with attendees highlighting their appreciation for the combination of presentations, discussions and opportunity for informal conversations over drinks and snacks. Many also expressed a strong interest in similar future events, recognizing them as valuable platforms for fostering mutual understanding.

4.1.2 Finland

In the Finnish study area, the municipalities of Kuusamo, Posio and Rovaniemi, there is intensive mineral exploration but no mining activity. The aim of the events organised in the area has been to inform people about the objectives and research of the AGEMERA project, but above all to give local people the opportunity to discuss the issue, the disadvantages and the benefits of possible mining. The Rovaniemi event was held in the village of Muurola, the largest village in the southern part of the municipality, near the Mawson Ltd's Rajapalot mining project on 22 May 2025. Nearly 50 people (n=46) had gathered, and the event was particularly critical of the mine. People were concerned about the impact of single and multiple mining projects on the Kemijoki River, the knowledge of new local councillors on mining issues, and the need for organised advocacy for local people in mining related issues.

In Kuusamo, in the village of Käylä, where the Juomasuo mine has been planned for decades, 39 local residents attended the event on 5 June 2025. Based on quantitative and qualitative research conducted in the AGEMERA project, the people of Kuusamo value their clean nature, believe in the development of nature-based tourism and consider the Juomasuo mine a threat to local livelihoods. Participants confirmed these findings and appreciated the fact that the studies communicated their concerns.

4.1.3 Estonia

TalTech organised a series of targeted seminars and workshops aimed at raising awareness of CRMs among diverse audiences, including citizens, educators, students, and civil society representatives. These activities were designed to foster a deeper understanding of the role of minerals in modern life and the importance of sustainable raw material management.

One of the key events was the **AGEMERA Webinar for Teachers**, held on **5 December 2024**, titled “Minerals Got Talent: Where Does the Fork Come From?” (Figure 8). This interactive and engaging online session introduced the concept of CRMs and their everyday relevance. The webinar featured presentations on global challenges driving mineral demand, the use of minerals in sectors ranging from construction to food production, mining technologies, environmental and social impacts, circular economy principles, and the importance of raw materials in the green transition. Topics such as the Critical Raw Materials Act, Rare Earth Elements, battery materials, and the concept of SLE\SLO were also addressed. As part of the session, participants engaged in an interactive e-learning workshop, where they matched specific minerals to everyday objects – such as the fork to mineral magnetite – to better understand their origin, properties, and significance.

Figure 8. AGEMERA Webinar for Teachers visual.

On 6 May 2025, TalTech hosted the **AGEMERA Open Innovation Seminar “Exploring Tomorrow: Innovations in Mineral Tech and Beyond”** (Figure 9). This event brought together researchers, industry leaders, and innovators to discuss cutting-edge developments in mineral exploration, data visualisation, and sustainable resource management. The seminar showcased AGEMERA project achievements and provided a platform for dialogue on the future of CRM technologies. Presentations were followed by a panel discussion exploring motivations and opportunities in the evolving raw materials landscape.

Figure 9. AGEMERA Open Innovation Seminar “Exploring Tomorrow: Innovations in Mineral Tech and Beyond” visual.

Another major initiative was the **AGEMERA Critical Raw Materials and Smartphone Life Cycle Game Introduction Seminar**, held on 5 June 2025 (Figure 10). This interactive session introduced an educational online game that follows the life cycle of a smartphone, using it as a tool to illustrate the sourcing, use, and recycling of critical raw materials. Participants gained insights into the raw materials behind everyday technologies and how circular economy principles can be applied to reduce environmental impact.

Figure 10. AGEMERA Critical Raw Materials and Smartphone Life Cycle Game Introduction Seminar visual.

In addition to these flagship events, TalTech conducted numerous in-person **workshops** titled “**Minerals Got Talent: Where Does the Fork Come From?**” for 254 students and 13 teachers, both at TalTech and in schools and public venues across Estonia (Figure 11). These workshops combined lectures and hands-on activities, helping participants understand the global relevance of minerals, their link to everyday objects, and their role in the green transition. A simplified version of the workshop was also featured in

conference exhibition areas and outreach events across Estonia and internationally, reaching approximately 250 people from varied backgrounds.

Figure 11. Collage of various events featuring the workshop “Minerals Got Talent: Where Does the Fork Come From?” and conference exhibitions held across Estonia.

4.1.4 Zambia

On 13 June 2025, the AGEMERA project held its final dissemination seminar in Lusaka, Zambia, titled “AGEMERA Final Results Showcase: Innovation, Impact & Zambia–Europe Collaboration for Sustainable Critical Raw Materials Development.” Organised in collaboration with the University of Zambia and the University of Oulu, the event brought together stakeholders from the mining industry, academia, government institutions, and civil society, both on-site at the Radisson Blu Hotel and online.

The aim of the event was to present the project’s final results and explore future collaboration opportunities between Europe and Zambia to promote responsible and sustainable CRM development. The seminar featured three thematic sessions: (1) Geophysical methods and innovations for mineral exploration, showcasing non-invasive

technologies used for subsurface characterisation; (2) Geological field and laboratory studies, focusing on field data from test sites and analytical results; and (3) Social dimensions of CRMs and the green and digital transition, highlighting public engagement, stakeholder involvement, and the concept of SLO. The event was attended by experts from both Europe and Zambia, including representatives from the Zambian Ministry of Mining, the Embassy of Finland in Lusaka, and the Association of Women in Mining in Africa. The event marked a significant milestone in the project, reinforcing the value of international collaboration in building a more sustainable and resilient raw materials sector.

4.1.5 Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, two public awareness events related to CRMs were organised by the Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences as part of the AGEMERA project activities. The first event took place on 22 April 2025 to mark **International Earth Day**. Held at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, the conference brought together representatives from the Bulgarian Mining and Geological Chamber, the Ministry of Energy, the Embassy of Finland, and scientific institutions. In addition to presentations on national initiatives and the strategic importance of CRMs, the event also featured a talk by AGEMERA project lead Jari Joutsenvaara and demonstrations of exploration technologies developed within the AGEMERA project.

The second public engagement activity occurred during the **Sofia Science Festival** on 10–11 May 2025. BAS hosted a demonstration stand under the theme “Critical and Strategic Raw Materials: From the Ore to the Tailing.” As part of the exhibit, AGEMERA project materials were presented through brochures, banners, and an interactive online game about CRMs and mobile phone lifecycle. Visitors had the opportunity to learn about the role of CRMs in modern society and explore a range of raw materials, waste products, and final applications. The AGEMERA stand successfully contributed to raising public awareness about sustainable mineral exploration, especially among younger audiences, and promoted the project's innovative approaches within the broader scientific and educational outreach of the festival.

4.2 Communication Strategies

To ensure a wide outreach and boost engagement, targeted communication activities were conducted by partners in charge of the event organisation at local level, with support from GEONARDO. Pre-event, partners would organise a series of internal meetings to decide on the target audiences, the dissemination and/or communication materials needed for the event, the key messages aimed to capture audiences' attention, and the various activities deployed to promote the event and attract participants. Communication materials were tailored to fit each target group; they were translated or produced directly into local languages (e.g. in the case of Germany), and would reflect the project's progress at that particular time, with more focus on tangible

results once those were available (e.g. A6 brochures were produced for the event in Zambia, focusing on the results of the project, while existing material was adapted for a Zambian audience). Targeted email campaigns were initiated to connect with and invite potential guests directly, whereas online promotion was used to expand the audience pool and spark interest in both the project and CRM in the broader sense (Figure 12). Dedicated social media campaigns were conducted across AGEMERA channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, X) to announce the events, the topics they dealt with, the agenda, speakers, as well as administrative details regarding registration (forms, deadlines, links).

Figure 12. Social media carousel to promote the AGEMERA Results Showcase event in Lusaka.

For example, The “Discussionsrunde - Annau kritischer Rohstoffe im Ergebirge” event’s outreach was carried out in three stages. First, potential interested mining companies were contacted directly and asked to share the contact details of other interested stakeholders. In the second phase, these stakeholders were contacted directly. In the final stage, information about the event was shared via the university’s press office, the City of Freiberg’s website, and social media. This approach allowed us to directly target those involved in the mining industry and those affected by it.

In addition, a webpage was created where people could register, as displayed in Figure 13.

Diskussionsrunde - Abbau kritischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge

Startseite / Fakultät für Geowissenschaften, Geotechnik und Bergbau / Institute / Institut für Bergbau und Spezialtiefbau / Rohstoffabbau und Spezialverfahren unter Tage / Veranstaltungen / AGEMERA - Öffentliche Diskussionsrunde

5. März 2025: Öffentliche Veranstaltung Abbau kritischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge - Was sagen Sie dazu?

Wir freuen uns, Sie auf unsere Diskussionsrunde zum Thema "Abbau kritischer Rohstoffe im Erzgebirge" am **05. März 2025** aufmerksam machen zu dürfen und laden Sie herzlich ein. In dieser Veranstaltung möchten wir zusammen mit Ihnen und **Vertretern von Bergbauunternehmen** und der **sächsischen Bergverwaltung** ins Gespräch kommen und über die **Herausforderungen, Chancen und Auswirkungen** des Abbaus kritischer Rohstoffe im **Erzgebirge** diskutieren.

Ihre Meinung ist uns wichtig! Nutzen Sie die Gelegenheit, sich zu informieren, Ihre Ansichten einzubringen und mit anderen Teilnehmenden sowie Fachleuten ins Gespräch zu kommen.

Sie haben auch die Möglichkeit, Beiträge bei der Anmeldung einzureichen.

[Einladung & Programm →](#)

[Zur Anmeldung →](#)

Organisation und Kontakt

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Figure 13. Website used to disseminate the AGEMERA event in Freiberg, Germany.

The event website for the public discussion in Freiberg provided key information about the date, location, and purpose of the event. It included a detailed agenda, speaker list, and a registration form allowing participants to submit questions or comments in advance. The site also offered downloadable materials about AGEMERA and the event and included contact details.

4.3 Measuring Impact: Participant Feedback and Recognition of Engagement

As part of the various workshops, seminars, and public events, feedback questionnaires were administered to participants both before and after the sessions. These surveys aimed to assess changes in knowledge, gauge participants' perceptions, and gather suggestions for improving the content and delivery of the workshops. In some cases, certificates of attendance were also provided to acknowledge participants' engagement and learning outcomes.

4.3.1 Design and Implementation of Participation Surveys

Participation questionnaires were developed for various events; however, due to time constraints, they were primarily implemented during student workshops.

For the workshop “Where Does the Fork Come From?”, pre- and post-workshop questionnaires were developed to assess participants' prior knowledge and compare it with learning outcomes after the session. The questionnaires were primarily conducted in Estonian to ensure accessibility and relevance for local participants.

Figure 14. Pre-lecture questionnaire opening page screenshot.

The questions asked before conducting the workshop:

1. What comes to your mind when you hear the term ‘critical raw materials’?
2. What industries do you know that are heavily dependent on critical raw materials? If you're not sure, feel free to make an educated guess.
3. Can you name any critical raw materials and their common uses? If you're not sure, feel free to make an educated guess.

4. How do you think critical raw materials impact our daily lives and the economy? If you're not sure, feel free to make an educated guess.
5. What are your thoughts on the environmental impact of critical raw material extraction?

Figure 15. Post-lecture questionnaire opening page screenshot.

The questions asked after the workshop:

1. What was the most surprising fact you learned today about critical raw materials?
2. How do you think the information presented today will influence your personal or professional decisions?
3. What role can individuals play in ensuring the responsible use of critical raw materials?
4. What actions do you think are necessary to raise public awareness about the importance of critical raw materials?
5. Other observations and feedback

4.3.2 Survey Results and Learning Outcomes

For the workshop “Where Does the Fork Come From?”, the **pre-workshop questionnaire** gathered a total of 161 responses across seven different sessions. Due to time constraints, not all workshops were able to complete the questionnaire. The variety of responses reflects an emerging awareness of the role and impact of CRMs, while also highlighting a clear need for further education and public outreach – particularly to strengthen understanding among younger audiences and those without prior expertise.

1. What comes to your mind when you hear the term ‘critical raw materials’?

Most respondents associated CRMs with natural resources or minerals that are rare, essential, or becoming scarce. Many linked CRMs to geology, mining, oil, and energy, while others connected the term to economic importance or environmental issues. A significant portion, however, admitted they did not know what the term meant or felt confused by the word "critical."

2. What industries do you know that are heavily dependent on critical raw materials?

The industries most frequently mentioned were energy production, electronics, construction, and mining, followed by transport, food, and technology sectors. A few respondents also highlighted healthcare, defence, agriculture, and textile industries. Several answers pointed out that almost all industries today rely on CRMs in some way.

3. Can you name any critical raw materials and their common uses?

Commonly cited CRMs included oil, coal, gold, lithium, iron, uranium, and phosphorite. Their uses ranged from fuel, electricity, and construction to electronics, household items (like forks), and everyday technologies. Many respondents were unsure and could not name specific materials or their applications, though some suggested everyday uses like cutlery, fuel, and furniture.

4. How do you think critical raw materials impact our daily lives and the economy?

Participants generally agreed that CRMs are deeply integrated into daily life and essential to economic functioning. Responses pointed out how CRMs affect product availability, prices, energy access, and technological progress. Some noted that if certain raw materials run out or prices rise, it could disrupt living standards and the broader economy.

5. What are your thoughts on the environmental impact of critical raw material extraction?

Many participants expressed concerns about the environmental consequences of mining, mentioning air pollution, habitat destruction, CO₂ emissions, and climate change. Some called for more sustainable practices, while others accepted the impacts as necessary but in need of mitigation. A few responses emphasized the importance of finding a balance between extraction and environmental protection or even reducing consumption overall.

Regarding the **post-workshop questionnaire**, the results indicate that participants gained new knowledge. Across the seven workshops where there was sufficient time to conduct the questionnaire, a total of 153 participants submitted their responses. It appears that eight participants did not complete the post-questionnaire.

1. What was the most surprising fact you learned today about critical raw materials?

Participants were most surprised to learn that shale oil from Estonia is used in hair dye. Many also discovered that polyester is made from oil, bread contains phosphate, and oil shale is used in cosmetics. Some were astonished that clay shale contains uranium, and that common household items like forks or matches contain mined materials such as magnetite or sulphur. The enormous scale of mining operations, the diverse origins of materials in everyday products, and the idea that precious metals like gold exist in Estonia were eye-opening. Discovering that the USSR may have used Estonian uranium in nuclear programs was also a notable insight.

2. How do you think the information presented today will influence your personal or professional decisions?

Many students admitted the workshop won't directly change their career plans, but it raised awareness of the materials behind everyday objects. Several participants noted that they'll now think more critically about where things come from, and some became more interested in geology or sustainability-related careers. A few expressed curiosities about urban mining, such as extracting metals from old phones. While not everyone saw a major impact, many gained new perspectives and felt more informed about how the material world functions.

3. What role can individuals play in ensuring the responsible use of critical raw materials?

The most common answers emphasized recycling, reuse, and reducing consumption. Participants recognized the importance of bringing old electronics to proper recycling points, buying only what is needed, and using items for as long as possible. Several highlighted the need to support responsible companies, educate themselves, and avoid wasteful habits. Some suggested protesting against unethical mining or raising awareness about the human and environmental costs tied to resource extraction. Others stressed the value of conscious consumption and circular economy practices.

4. What actions do you think are necessary to raise public awareness about the importance of critical raw materials?

Participants proposed more workshops, lectures, school lessons, and media campaigns. Many stressed the need for accessible and engaging education, using real-life examples, statistics, and visual materials to explain where raw materials come from and why they matter. Suggestions included social media campaigns, informative posters, school programs, TV segments, and public events. Some pointed out that presenting relatable comparisons and connecting the topic to people's daily lives would help make the issue more understandable and urgent.

5. Other observations and feedback

Overall, feedback was overwhelmingly positive. Participants described the workshop as fun, educational, and eye-opening. They appreciated the interactive format, the chance to handle real materials, and the way the topic was made engaging and relevant. A few suggested logistical improvements (e.g., missing materials or unclear instructions), but most were enthusiastic and eager for more such activities in the future. Many said the session helped them see the world differently and made them think deeper about the impact of their daily choices.

The comparison between pre- and post-workshop questionnaire responses highlights notable shifts in knowledge, attitudes, and awareness:

- Before the workshop, most students had little to no prior knowledge about critical raw materials. Many were unfamiliar with the term entirely or confused raw materials with finished products. After the workshop, however, students were able to identify specific critical raw materials – such as bauxite, phosphate, and cobalt – and connect them to everyday products like phones, hair dye, or clothing. Surprising facts, like the use of Estonian oil shale in cosmetics or uranium in clay shale, stood out and stayed with the participants, demonstrating a significant increase in factual knowledge.
- Initially, participants struggled to see how these materials related to their everyday lives. Few recognized that the objects they use daily come from mined resources. After the session, there was a clear shift in perspective. Many reported being surprised by how widespread the use of mined materials is and reflected on the origins of things like bread, electronics, or textiles. They became more aware of how intimately geology and resource extraction are tied to modern lifestyles.
- In terms of personal or career impact, most students initially believed the topic would not influence them. Afterward, while some still said their plans would remain unchanged, others expressed a newfound interest in geology, sustainability, or the mining sector. A few mentioned they were inspired to learn more or even consider studying something related to earth sciences or circular economy, indicating that the workshop broadened their horizon of possibilities.
- Environmental responsibility was previously mentioned in general terms, with basic ideas like “recycling” or “not wasting.” After the workshop, responses became more detailed and thoughtful. Students began discussing the importance of recycling electronics, making sustainable consumer choices, and thinking critically about overconsumption. Some even referenced ethical issues such as child labour in cobalt mining, showing a deeper understanding of the global implications of raw material use.

- Before the workshop, participants struggled to suggest ways to raise awareness about critical raw materials. Many left that question blank or simply answered “I don’t know.” Afterward, however, students had concrete ideas: creating more workshops, holding lectures in schools, launching media campaigns, and making better use of social media to educate the public. They recognized that raising awareness is a key part of the solution.

In conclusion, the workshop succeeded in making a complex topic relatable and memorable. It not only improved students’ knowledge but also helped them understand the ethical and environmental aspects of material use. Many left with new questions, greater awareness, and even interest in pursuing related paths. The session empowered them to think critically about their own consumption and to contribute to a more responsible, circular future.

4.3.3 Certificates of Attendance as Recognition Tools

As part of various AGEMERA events, participants had the opportunity to receive a certificate of attendance, either upon request or by default. A certificate was issued following the AGEMERA Webinar for Teachers, held on 5 December 2024, titled “Minerals Got Talent: Where Does the Fork Come From?”. Similarly, after the science teachers’ workshop on 27 February 2025, certificates were offered to all participating teachers upon request.

The certificate serves as official recognition of participation, which can be used for professional development records, teaching portfolios, or to support continuing education credits depending on local requirements. An example of the AGEMERA certificate issued by TalTech is shown in Figure 16.

An example of the certificate of attendance issued for the event held in Germany is shown in Figure 17. Upon exiting the event, attendees were asked whether they would like to receive a certificate. Out of 100 participants, 22 requested and were issued a certificate of attendance.

Figure 16. Certificate of participation for AGEMERA events at TalTech.

Figure 17. Certificate of Attendance from the TUBAF event, with the signature of a TUBAF representative blacked out.

4.4 Social Media Campaigns and Digital Communication Strategies

Throughout the entire project, AGEMERA implemented a structured digital communication strategy — coordinated by Geonardo Environmental Technologies (GEO) — to complement public awareness events and significantly expand outreach beyond the countries where these events were held. Social media served as a key vehicle to raise awareness about critical raw materials: what they are, their role in citizens' daily lives and in the green and digital transition, and how AGEMERA has been uncovering Europe's and Zambia's CRM potential through non-invasive, environmentally friendlier exploration methods. These efforts aimed to make the project's contributions accessible to non-specialist audiences and to build broader public engagement with the challenges and opportunities surrounding CRM development.

4.4.1 #AGEMERAexplains social media campaign

One of the key elements of AGEMERA's digital outreach was the **#AGEMERAexplains** social media campaign, designed to demystify core concepts central to the project's mission. While terms like “twin transition” and “strategic minerals” may be familiar to professionals in the mining and exploration sectors, they are often unclear to the general public. To address this, the campaign featured carousel-style posts — visually structured sequences that users could swipe or click through — presenting these concepts in plain, accessible language and with appealing visual design. Many of the same terms were also included in the evolving **Glossary** on the AGEMERA website, reinforcing the project's broader effort to increase public understanding of critical raw materials and their relevance to Europe's green and digital transitions.

4.4.2 Video Communication Strategy and Outputs

In recent years, videos have become central to digital communication strategies, particularly due to decreasing attention spans and the growing preference for audiovisual content over static imagery. In line with this trend, GEO, in close collaboration with AGEMERA project partners, has led the development of several videos to raise awareness about the project's goals, technologies, and societal dimensions among a broader public. The original videos and current versions are available on the project's [YouTube channel](#).

- **AGEMERA: Critical Raw Materials for Stronger Europe**

The **first project video**, launched within the first year, introduced AGEMERA's overall approach using a “problem-solution” narrative. It highlighted Europe's critical dependence on third countries for critical raw materials, negative public perceptions of mining, and the urgency for more sustainable exploration methods. In response, the video presented AGEMERA's solutions—non-invasive technologies, stakeholder engagement, and awareness-raising campaigns—as key innovations. To increase accessibility among non-English-speaking audiences, the video was subtitled in

Bulgarian, Polish, and Spanish (Figure 18). It is available on AGEMERA’s YouTube channel and has been organically disseminated via social media, where it has gathered over 1,000 views. The development of the video was coordinated by GEO, with multiple feedback rounds involving partner contributions.

Figure 18. AGEMERA: *Critical Raw Materials for Stronger Europe* video was the first video published by the project. The video has been translated to Bulgarian, Polish and Spanish along with the original English.

- **Between Riches and Risks: Local Perspectives on Mineral Exploration**

The **second video** focused on the social dimension of the project, exploring local perspectives on mining and exploration through a storytelling approach. Inspired by real responses from the AGEMERA survey, it depicted two hypothetical characters to reflect the diverse hopes, concerns, and viewpoints of affected communities. This video aimed to promote understanding of how multiple stakeholder views can coexist and should be addressed. It was showcased during **EU Raw Materials Week 2024** in Brussels (9–13 December) and subsequently released via YouTube and social platforms, where it received more than 800 views.

Figure 19. In AGEMERA, we set out to discover how local communities in regions where mining activities take place feel about exploration in their region. More often than not, this is not a black and white story - but one that incorporates multiple perspectives.

- **Technology-focused videos**

In addition to these thematic videos, two technology-focused videos were also produced to promote AGEMERA’s innovative methods for sustainable mineral exploration, specifically targeting non-specialist audiences. These videos aimed to both explain how the technologies work and highlight their benefits, particularly in terms of efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and reduced environmental impact.

“Sky’s the limit: Why drones are revolutionising geophysical surveys”

The first video, developed in close collaboration with Radai, focused on drone-based geophysical surveys. It demonstrated how this approach offers a more sustainable alternative to traditional ground-based or airborne surveys. Using a combination of real and stock footage, expert commentary, and visualised data, the video illustrated how drone technology can make mineral exploration faster, more cost-efficient, and less harmful to the environment.

Figure 20. AGEMERA & Radai - Sky's the limit: Why drones are revolutionising geophysical surveys.

The **second technology video**, co-produced with **Muon Solutions**, introduced the principle and advantages of **muon imaging** technology. It explained how muons—naturally occurring subatomic particles—can be used to scan subsurface geology without the need for invasive drilling, making the process more sustainable and less disruptive to the environment.

“Detecting the Unseen. How muon imaging is transforming mineral exploration”

The **second technology-focused video**, produced in close collaboration with **Muon Solutions**, introduced the concept and application of **muon imaging technology**, which has been used in AGEMERA’s fieldwork. The video explained what muons are—naturally occurring subatomic particles—and how they can be harnessed to scan subsurface geology non-invasively. By eliminating the need for disruptive drilling, muon imaging offers a more sustainable and environmentally friendly approach to mineral exploration.

Figure 21. AGEMERA x Muon Solutions: *Detecting the Unseen. How muon imaging is transforming mineral exploration.*

All four videos featured a blend of expert footage, infographics, and accessible narration. They are publicly available on [AGEMERA's YouTube channel](#) and have been actively promoted through the project's social media channels to maximise outreach.

4.4.3 Other social media activities

International Days—typically designated by organisations such as the United Nations, UNESCO, or EU institutions—are intended to raise awareness of specific global issues. These observances often come with communication kits and dedicated hashtags, enabling coordinated outreach and increased visibility across social media platforms.

AGEMERA has actively leveraged these opportunities to amplify its awareness-raising efforts. For example, on the **World Day for Safety and Health at Work** (28 April 2025), the project highlighted how its **non-invasive technologies** not only reduce environmental impact but also improve safety for workers involved in mineral exploration. A dedicated **social media carousel** was created for the occasion to communicate these messages clearly and accessibly.

The poster features the AGEMERA logo in the top left corner. Below it, the date "28 April 2025" is displayed. The main title, "World Day for Safety and Health at Work", is prominently shown in a white box with an orange background. A photograph of a yellow hard hat and a red first aid kit on a construction site is positioned to the right of the text. At the bottom left, the text "Did you know that..." is followed by an orange arrow pointing to the right. At the bottom right, the text "Find out more at agemera.eu/technologies" is displayed in orange.

...the methods and technologies we use in AGEMERA for mineral exploration are not only more environmentally friendly, but also pose **no threat** to workers' safety, as opposed to traditional exploration methods?

Figure 22. Use of international days to raise awareness of important, as occupational safety, and interesting, as e.g. Happy International Rock Day.

4.5 Making an Impact through Collaboration: Strategic Partnerships in Europe and Beyond

AGEMERA's commitment to trust-building and long-term societal engagement extends well beyond its project boundaries, positioning it as a strategic contributor on both European and global stages. As a founding member of ESMIN – the European Sustainable Mining & Innovation Network – the project actively supports the development of a more inclusive, transparent, and socially responsible mineral exploration framework across Europe.

4.5.1 European-Level Collaboration

AGEMERA has participated in a number of high-impact European collaborations, events, and networking activities that help amplify its messages and increase its relevance among institutional, industrial, and research communities:

EU Supercluster Lapland Geoconference 2024

AGEMERA co-organised this major event, which brought together over 140 participants to discuss the intersection of raw materials, regional development, and sustainability

challenges in the European North. The conference served as a high-level forum for policy exchange, stakeholder dialogue, and future collaboration opportunities.

EGU General Assembly 2025

At the European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2025, AGEMERA co-initiated and co-led a dedicated session focused on collaborative approaches in raw materials research and stakeholder engagement. The session attracted 69 participants (onsite and online) and featured presentations from 10 EU and national-level projects. It was co-organised by Horizon Europe projects AGEMERA, MultiMiner, EIS, GoldenRAM, AVANTIS, LITHOS, and EXCEED, alongside Finnish initiatives including the JTF-funded “Development of the Extractive Industry in Lapland, Northern Ostrobothnia and Kainuu (KAKE)” and the ERDF-funded Lapland Mining Hub.

Horizon Europe Clustering and Joint Outreach

AGEMERA has maintained close collaboration with peer projects such as MINE.IO, ADMA3, MultiMiner, SEMACRET, and others through joint webinars, shared promotional campaigns, and thematic clustering activities. These efforts facilitate mutual visibility, enhance alignment with EU policy goals, and support the exchange of technical and social innovations in CRM exploration.

Smart Specialisation Platform (S3P) – Mining Regions

AGEMERA contributes to the S3P Mining Regions initiative to ensure that its outputs align with regional innovation agendas. This collaboration helps connect project outcomes with local development strategies and enhances policy relevance across European mining regions.

4.5.2 Global Outreach and Policy Influence

AGEMERA has also engaged in strategic international events and forums, contributing to global policy discussions and sustainable development goals in the mineral exploration sector:

UNECE Resource Management Week 2024

AGEMERA presented its educational and ESG-related activities at this international forum, highlighting the integration of UNFC and UNRMS resource classification frameworks into academic curricula and stakeholder engagement initiatives. The UNECE participation came through presentation on implementing the UNFC and UNRMS into the AGEMERA university courses, and through panel discussion about the role of HEIs in educating UNFC and UNRMS. The UNECE have recently launched a

Knowledge hub, were UNFC and UNRMS implementation from the academy are collected. AGEMERA project has been one of the first ones.

PDAC 2025, Canada

As part of the EU delegation, AGEMERA participated in the Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada (PDAC) convention – one of the world’s most prominent mineral exploration events. The project used the platform to showcase its non-invasive exploration techniques, digital engagement approaches, and sustainability-driven communication strategies.

OECD Mining Regions and Cities Initiative

Reflecting its growing recognition, AGEMERA’s coordinator was invited by the OECD to contribute to the Mining Regions and Cities fact-finding mission (2023). At the closing seminar held in Rovaniemi, Finland (July 2025), AGEMERA presented its regional survey results, offering insights into public attitudes, social acceptance, and local perspectives on mining and exploration. This participation underscores AGEMERA’s emerging role in shaping international policy dialogue on responsible resource governance.

5 Conclusion

The AGEMERA project has taken significant strides in fostering awareness, education, and social engagement around CRMs through an integrated approach that combines various stakeholders, interdisciplinary education, and targeted public outreach. These efforts have contributed to better understanding of the complex social, environmental, and technological dimensions of CRM exploration and usage in Europe and beyond. The following conclusion provides an overview of the results and reflections on the three core activities discussed in this report: questionnaire implementation in the case study regions, development of university courses, and organisation of public awareness events.

5.1 Questionnaires

The final survey round conducted in the AGEMERA case study regions – Estonia, Germany, and Finland – aimed to assess changes in public awareness, attitudes, and perceptions toward CRMs and related mining activities, particularly before and after educational or outreach interventions. The results were mixed in terms of both reach and depth. In Germany and Finland, the questionnaires were effectively promoted and received relatively strong participation rates, providing useful insights into how public opinion can shift through well-structured engagement strategies. Respondents demonstrated growing awareness of environmental, economic, and societal implications related to CRM sourcing.

In contrast, the Estonian survey yielded fewer responses due to several compounding factors. A politically sensitive environment surrounding phosphorite exploration created reluctance among the local population to engage, and a more cautious communication approach was taken to avoid unintended backlash. As a result, only around 50 were gathered, many of which were incomplete due to non-mandatory questions, limiting the dataset's usefulness for further analysis. Nevertheless, the low engagement level itself is indicative of public scepticism and underlines the need for trust-building and transparent communication in areas with contested mining histories.

These survey efforts underscore the importance of tailoring outreach and data collection strategies to regional socio-political contexts. The experience also reinforces the need for continuous public dialogue when seeking to secure the social licence to explore and operate.

5.2 Developed University Courses

A major outcome of the AGEMERA project was the successful development and pilot implementation of university-level educational programmes focused on CRMs. These included the “European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition”

course offered by TUBAF and the “Sustainable Exploration, Mining and Circular Economy of Mineral Resources” micro-degree provided by TalTech. Both initiatives aimed to embed interdisciplinary, up-to-date content into higher education to prepare future professionals for addressing complex challenges in CRM supply, sustainability, and governance.

The TUBAF course adopted a modular structure and was offered in hybrid format, combining lectures from AGEMERA partners with student interaction and performance evaluation through feedback, mini-tests, and certification. It incorporated cutting-edge case studies on digital innovation, corporate responsibility, environmental management, and stakeholder engagement in the mining sector. Student feedback reflected strong appreciation for the course's relevance, although time constraints and scheduling posed some limitations to participation in optional modules.

TalTech’s micro-degree, launched in September 2024 and repeated in early 2025, attracted a growing number of students. The course provided an in-depth view of the full material value chain, from exploration technologies like passive seismic and muon imaging to circular economy concepts, resource efficiency, and policy frameworks. Self-paced learning, combined with assignments and reflective essays, allowed participants to engage flexibly while receiving certification upon completion. Feedback highlighted the high quality of content and its direct applicability to both industry and research paths.

Together, these courses highlight the significant role academic institutions can play in advancing Europe’s green and digital transition by equipping learners with the essential knowledge and skills required in a CRM-driven economy. Interdisciplinary education is fundamental – not only for geologists and engineers, but also for policymakers, environmental professionals, and the wider public – in tackling the complex, cross-sectoral challenges tied to Europe’s CRM strategy. Their continued development and expansion beyond the project timeline will be vital for building long-term educational infrastructure in this field.

5.3 Organisation of Public Awareness Events

Public engagement formed a core pillar of AGEMERA’s approach to improving understanding and acceptance of CRM-related activities. A wide array of workshops, seminars, and outreach events were conducted by partner institutions in Estonia, Germany, Finland, Bulgaria, Zambia, and other locations. These activities sought to build bridges between scientists, industry representatives, civil society, and policymakers by addressing both the benefits and challenges of CRM extraction and usage.

In Germany, TUBAF organised public discussions in the mining region of Saxony, where strong interest was observed among local citizens. Participants expressed a desire for transparent communication and inclusion in decision-making processes, particularly regarding how mining may affect their communities in the future. The events facilitated

constructive dialogue between mining companies and residents, highlighting the potential for socially inclusive CRM development when trust and participation are prioritised.

In Estonia, TalTech organised a series of workshops and seminars tailored to students and educators. The “Minerals Got Talent: Where Does the Fork Come From?” interactive workshop received highly positive feedback, with participants continuing to discuss the topics after the events. Teachers, in particular, welcomed the opportunity to integrate CRM content into their curricula and invited workshop facilitators to their classrooms, demonstrating a multiplier effect in educational outreach.

In Bulgaria, AGEMERA was represented at two major events organised by the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences: the International Earth Day conference and the Sofia Science Festival. These events drew participation from academic, governmental, and public sectors and provided a platform to present AGEMERA's findings, technologies, and public awareness tools, including educational games and brochures.

In Zambia, AGEMERA's final results seminar in Lusaka facilitated international cooperation by bringing together experts, diplomats, and industry stakeholders to explore future collaboration in sustainable resource management.

5.4 Social media and video campaigns

Overall, Geonardo's digital communication actions substantially supported the project's awareness and outreach goals. The combined reach of social media posts and videos surpassed 1800 views, with additional engagement through likes, shares, and comments. These activities played a complementary role to physical awareness events, amplifying the message across regions not directly involved in AGEMERA fieldwork.

Overall, the public outreach component of AGEMERA successfully engaged diverse target groups and demonstrated the value of inclusive dialogue, participatory education, and international exchange in shaping the future of CRM exploration.

5.5 European and global impact

Through these multi-level activities—local, regional, European, and global—AGEMERA has positioned itself as a pan-European actor at the intersection of science, society, and policy. Its contributions promote transparency, innovation, and best practices for the responsible exploration and management of critical raw materials.

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